

Case Study 6: Process Recording and Digital Research Notebooks

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Case Study Outline

The main aims of this case study were to:

- Assess process recording requirements and the associated digital landscape
- Investigate Digital Research Notebooks and evaluate the suitability of generic recording systems to support diverse workflows

This was achieved through a combination of a systematic literature review, an investigation of the available tools and technologies and a user survey for the physical sciences community. This survey was built upon several past research studies conducted by the Frey Group and was designed to understand how (if at all) the current landscape has shifted over the past few years.

This report begins by setting out our background and motivation, explaining why this research is so important to the physical sciences community. In Section 1, we provide some historical context to the generation of the scientific record, and an assessment of the previous use of digital tools in scientific research; noting the remaining issues, and the changes that need to be made if we are going to improve the digitisation of scientific research. Section 2 delves into the user landscape explored within this work; describing the different user roles that need to be considered in the process of recording and digitising the scientific record, providing advice on how to involve the users at every step. Section 3 sets out additional research that was undertaken as part of this case study, which includes a current landscape assessment of Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs), and our survey on process recording. Section 4 describes the features that our community desires and Section 5 outlines some of the range of technologies that could be used to achieve this. We finish with our conclusions and recommendations in Section 6.

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1 Background

This case study was undertaken by members of the Frey and Coles Groups at the University of Southampton. These groups have extensive experience in researching different aspects of digitising the scientific record, both from a scientific and technical perspective; looking at user behaviour, investigating current systems, and identifying how different technologies can be used in this process. The team has been collectively working on research in this area for the last two decades, totalling over 80 years' experience across the group.

1.1 The Scientific Record

Progress in scientific endeavour builds upon the research that has gone before; fundamental to this process is the generation of the scientific record, the accumulation of information and knowledge through experimentation, measurement, and observation. This acquired knowledge needs to be shared with the community so that it can be validated and built upon. In what Latour and Woolgar call “a mania for inscription”, scientists methodically record their actions and activities¹. Throughout history most of these inscriptions have been captured in paper notebooks, but important contextual information for experiments or studies are also captured in the form of labels, inventories, data tables, diagrams, graphs, maps, and other documents. All these various inscriptions are captured on the way to the production of the formal documentation formats such as reports, papers, and conference presentations that we tend to think of as making up the scientific record.

Historically, the primary vehicle for the dissemination of scientific knowledge has been the journal article. Journal articles have limited space and have typically provided limited data and only high-level details of the methods involved in a particular experiment or study, often not enough to be able to replicate or even validate the study. The data within the journal articles are usually in the form of tables of numbers or graphs where a reader has to manually read and record the numbers if they want to reuse the information. Readers could request more complete data from a study, but in reality, a majority of authors would refuse the request or the data would not be provided in a format suitable for reuse².

As a stronger emphasis has been placed on data sharing, many journals introduced requirements for data to be provided in the form of Supplementary Information linked to the journal article, but problems remain. For example, much supplementary information is in PDF format with data still in the form of images and tables which are difficult to extract, and they are not machine-readable, so manual processes are still needed to determine if the data is relevant. It is also difficult to determine whether the data is licensed for reuse.

Sharing the data in theory allows other researchers to be able to verify and validate the data, replicate the results of others, and apply new methods to the data to find new knowledge. However, sharing the data alone is not sufficient. Without appropriate context most data are completely meaningless. In order to ensure that data is reproducible and meaningful it is essential that the data is provided together with information about how the data was created, how it has been manipulated, and what the data means. Without this context it is much harder to understand the data, and as a result the data are much more likely to be misinterpreted or misunderstood. It is much more difficult and laborious to document the data after it has been produced. Most scientists capture information about the processes they use as they are carrying out their research, and this information should be provided with the data to provide the context about why and how the data was produced and what transformations it has undergone.

The archaic practice of storing the scientific record purely through paper records hinders the ability of scientists to gather and share their data and methods with the community. As more and more data is being generated using digital instruments, the various other inscriptions involved in recording the process are increasingly being captured through a myriad of digital information management systems³. However, these systems, where they exist, are often isolated and can create a significant disconnect between the data and experimental record. This creates difficulties at many stages of the data lifecycle and in particular, the process of preparing data and manuscripts for sharing and publication is manual and laborious.

1.2 Digital Solutions

Over the past 2 decades there has been an increasing realisation that digital tools can provide a solution to many of these problems, ensuring that data is effectively managed and coupled with the experiment or study record so that both can be shared together. Digital tools can also easily generate and capture appropriate metadata at all stages of the lifecycle to describe the data in detail and ensure that the data is machine-readable, so that it can easily be discovered and reused. Different kinds of research may need different kinds of tools, but a digital tool that can build upon and enhance the functionality of the paper notebook is an essential requirement for recording the processes and rationale behind scientific research. As such, a number of different types of digital tools have been created which can enhance the process of capturing the scientific record.

1.2.1 Electronic Lab Notebooks

In 2006⁴, Taylor noted ‘the paper-based lab book is the final component of the research and development (R&D) workflow that has yet to be digitised’. Electronic notebooks were created to serve as a digital replacement for the paper lab notebook and were initially described, at least in scientific literature, as a revolutionary solution. Myers et al⁵ noted that ELNs eliminate the need for manual transcription and can be used by widely distributed groups. Voegele et al⁶ describe ELNs as providing the ability to quickly enter, retrieve, locate and share data, in addition to facilitating long term storage through the creation of backups and archives.

1.2.1.1 Barriers to Adoption

However, despite these advantages, there have been many historic barriers to the adoption of ELNs that have resulted in a lack of uptake over the years, particularly in academia⁷, and led to ELNs having a poor reputation with respect to actually being useful.

Additionally, the ELN market has been over saturated for a long time, hundreds of ELNs have been in existence at any one time, and as such there was no “key player” in the market, like there is for word processing or spreadsheets (namely the big three, Google, Apple and Microsoft). This meant even for those who were potentially interested in using one, it was difficult to identify which one to use.

A survey conducted by Dial-a-Molecule in 2011⁷ that asked 169 participants about their thoughts on ELNs, showed that whilst 98% of the respondents were aware of ELNs, only 11% were actively using them; even if 76% were interested in finding out more about them or figuring out how to implement one. In 2016 a survey conducted by BioSistemika⁷ showed similar results in that only 7% of their participants were actively using an ELN, with 10% saying they were actively looking to use one and 62% saying they would think about it in the future. This shows little improvement in a 5-year span and this is almost certainly due to the barriers to entry not

having changed. The barriers categorised in Table 1 below came from this Dial-a-Molecule 2011 survey, and yet prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, most of these still remained firmly in place as barriers to using ELN systems.

Table 1: Categorised Barriers of ELN Adoption from the Dial a Molecule iLabber Pilot Project: Potential Uses of ELNs in Academia Survey from September 2011, adapted from (Kanza et al., 2017)

Barrier Category	Barrier Explanation	% of 169
Cost	Up-front costs and licensing fees	74%
	Additional infrastructure costs (e.g computers)	27%
	Future development and costs of application	90%
	Ongoing costs of the system	93%
ELN attitude	Only makes sense if the whole department adopts it	20%
	Belief that students/post docs would resist adoption	11%
Ease of Use	ELN was too difficult to use	22%
	Does not capture the right information for me	7%
	Hard to capture some types of information in ELNs	80%
ELN Access	Duplicated data entry across the lab / write-up area	74 %
	No easy access to appropriate hardware in the lab	12.5%
Data Compatibility	Data will be tied into a commercial package	84 %
Other	Other	11%

Cost

Cost has always been an issue with respect to ELNs⁷, both in terms of actual financial outlay, and hidden costs such as time to learn to use a new system or address any issues. Some ELNs cost an extortionate amount of money, and therefore whilst some well off companies might be willing to pay those prices, they are unlikely to be used in academic institutes. Especially as many ELNs are only suitable for certain disciplines, so paying for a subscription would likely entail paying for subscriptions to multiple different ELN platforms.

ELN Attitudes

People's attitudes to ELN are another huge barrier, there has historically been a much lower uptake of ELNs in academia, and often even if there is some enthusiasm in a group to use one, unless the entire group agrees it can be hard to organise implementing one. Academia is a much freer environment which is both a good and a bad thing, but this does mean that the attitudes of supervisors and group leaders have a significant influence on how researchers record their data, as often new group members will follow the current setup.

Ease of Use

There is a perception that capturing data in an ELN would be difficult, especially compared to the flexible affordances of paper. Paper enables completely free entry of text and data however the user desires. Users are likely to make scribble notes and sketches down on pieces of paper, something that is harder to achieve using an ELN.

ELN Access

Historically labs have often been seen as hostile environments for using an ELN. It is common for labs to be quite cluttered and for there to be lack of space to bring in a laptop or tablet to take notes with. Additionally, even if there is space, in labs where experiments are being conducted with chemicals, there is a lack of desire to risk one's technology by bringing it into the laboratory. This then leads to concern of needing to duplicate data entry (first on paper in the lab, and then onto a computer outside of the lab) if it is not possible to formalise the notetaking process in the lab itself.

Data Compatibility

It has often been a common practice of ELN developers to create their own proprietary data formats to lock users into their systems. This results in concerns that data created as part of an ELN won't be compatible with other systems, and that users will struggle to take their data out of an ELN if they wish to use it elsewhere or change systems because they will be unable to get it out in a usable format.

1.2.1.2 ELN Conclusions

ELNs are a well-used tool in industry for the capture and management of methods and data for experiments but is less well-used in research environments where experimental work may be less well structured.⁷ The ELNs used within industry are frequently discipline specific with rich toolsets designed to provide access to information sources and datatypes specific to those industries such as the pharmaceuticals industry and genetic research. However, due to the barriers noted above, in Section 1.2.1.1, they still remain unpopular in academia.

For the majority of these tools, there is limited end to end support for researchers in managing their research records and data across the lifecycle of their research. Some ELNs provide some features that are useful, but there are many more ways that researchers could be better supported by these tools, by enabling them to better plan and record their research, be supported during their research, enabling the import or linking to datasets, and ultimately the sharing and publication of both the research and the data.

1.2.2 Data Capture & Curation

As noted in Section 1.1, the scientific record is not merely comprised of the scrawlings in a paper lab notebook, it is as much about the data that is captured alongside that process. As such, the notion of digital curation has to be considered.

The term 'digital curation', as defined by the Digital Curation Centre^a, is the process of maintaining, preserving and adding value to digital research data throughout its lifecycle. Digital curation involves the steps taken to manage the data during and after the end of a project from planning through to preservation, sharing and reuse. These processes also add value to the data in the form of additional context that can assist in the discovery and usability of the data and

^a <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/about/digital-curation>

typically also involves the addition of metadata to describe the data itself and the transformations that it has undergone.

1.2.2.1 FAIR Data

A large driver of digital curation is to ensure the long-term preservation of data, but also interoperability and machine readability to ensure that data can be discovered and reused. The FAIR Guiding Principles, published in 2016⁸, provided guidance to the community on how to ensure data are effectively managed and made reusable for the benefit of future science. FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable and builds upon good data management and data curation behaviour, but with a focus on how data can be made discoverable, meaningful, and usable by machines. This focus on interoperability is to enable machines to do the work of finding and assessing whether datasets could be useful for particular scientific research, leaving researchers more time to focus on the science. The FAIR principles do not recommend specific technologies or standards to follow, but for chemistry there is a drive towards the 'FAIRification' of existing services. If services can avoid the use of proprietary formats and instead make use of persistent identifiers, metadata, and standard formats for data files and protocols for communication, then it makes it much more likely that data can be shared and effectively reused.

The adherence to FAIR has made some improvements to the quality of data produced by the physical sciences community, however, issues still remain⁹. As mentioned in Section 1.1 data is meaningless without the context that describes how the data was produced, and this extends beyond how the raw data was captured to how it has been selected, cleaned, processed, transformed, and analysed to produce the final data. Data are increasingly being generated through computational methods and data-intensive science such as simulations, modelling, and workflows. These data can be very complex and are often created in non-standard formats making them difficult to organise and understand. The software used to process and produce all such data is needed to make sense of the data and to replicate the results. This software includes not only standard analytical or workflow tools, but also the various tools, code and scripts that might have been used throughout the process. To be reusable and understandable, data must be provided together with the other resources that explain how it was created. The data also need to be shared in standard formats so that it be opened, read, and manipulated within standard software tools.

1.2.2.2 Metadata and provenance

It became obvious that if FAIR data was really to be achieved, then we also needed to consider to aspects of provenance and metadata. Capturing provenance trails that enable others to understand how a set of data was generated, by whom, and what has happened to it since its creation is a vital part of comprehensively capturing the full depth of the scientific record.

The provenance enables others to assess the quality and reliability of the data and enables proper credit to be given to the originators of the data when it is reused by others. Data can be reused and recombined in ways and for purposes that were never imagined by the originator, and provenance enables the full pathway of what has happened to the data from inception, through preservation, and onto reuse by others. Metadata is a crucial element of provenance and a key part of effective data management. Metadata provides a simplified descriptive representation of complex data in a form that can be understood by both humans and computers. Metadata describing data enables the data to be discovered, searched, organised and the provenance to be visible. There are a variety of different metadata that can be added to data to describe it and for different purposes throughout its lifecycle. For example, descriptive

metadata enables the content of the data to be understood and can be used for discovery and to determine suitability of use of the data. Structural and technical metadata provides information about file formats, encoding and relationship between different elements of data. Administrative and preservation metadata provide information about how the data has been managed, unique identifiers for the data and the provenance, and processes the data has undergone to enable long-term preservation. Metadata are often generated automatically by the instruments and software that capture, generate and transform the data, but 'user-defined metadata' can also be created manually to add additional and more meaningful context about the data.

However, metadata may often only be generated at the point that the data is prepared for deposition in a repository or database, and therefore may not be as accurate and descriptive as it could have been if metadata had been produced throughout its lifecycle. A lack of effective data management may mean that the raw data and related resources associated with the data may become disconnected and less likely to be shared together with the data. The sharing of data and findings only at the end of a project or long-term study also slows down the progress of research. The research itself cannot easily be validated and verified by the community, and as the process currently works, there may be little in the way of peer review. Useful data is not easily accessible to others until a late stage leading to potential duplication of effort and wasted resources.

For a large percentage of scientists, it is still a difficult task to effectively prepare and share their data. There is the so-called 'burden of curation' or 'metadata friction' where researchers reach the end of the project and are then asked to prepare their data to be shared with an unknown audience. Often this process does not occur until publication or when another researcher asks to view their research. At this stage it is much harder to change the data into a format suitable for sharing, to structure the data effectively, and to add the appropriate metadata to help the data to be found and utilised successfully. Even more laborious is to document the data with the details of how it was created, processed and analysed. Whilst researchers are using paper-based notebooks to record their processes and data are created digitally, there is a disconnect between the record and the data, and there is no easy way to turn the information captured into the notebook into useful documentation or metadata to describe the data. When the data is shared, it is unlikely to include the other resources that make it usable and understandable to others.

1.2.2.3 Data Capture & Curation Conclusions

In recent years, many more journals and funders, especially those providing grants from public money, have implemented requirements for authors preserving their full data in repositories and making it available to the community for reuse at publication time. This is in part due to FAIR and other initiatives raising awareness of the necessity of providing open and accessible data. There is also a requirement for many researchers and organisations to produce a Data Management Plan to describe what data will be collected and used, how it will be managed throughout a project, and how it will be preserved and under what conditions it will be shared after the end of the project.

The awareness of the need for standards, metadata and provenance is a step in the right direction. However, we still need to look at this process as a whole, as problems can arise when the focus is solely on the data, or indeed solely on the accompanying narrative.

There is the capacity to use digital tools to automatically capture vast amounts of valuable metadata and therefore the provenance trail. However, no one tool will provide all of the

functionality that scientists will need for their research, and interoperability is essential to ensure that researchers can make the most of functionality across different tools, but also that there is a seamless flow of data and supporting resources between different tools. Key to this is the use of standard formats and appropriate metadata.

1.3 Beyond the ELN

When considering how to encourage digitisation of the scientific record, the use of ELNs has always been a key recommendation. However, as discussed above and as demonstrated by nearly two decades of research collectively undertaken by our team at the University of Southampton, this hasn't proved overly successful. Whilst this is no doubt partially due to the fact that there is no all singing all dancing ELN that does everything a scientist needs, it nonetheless poses the question of are ELNs the answer?

More recent research by members of our team have shown that whilst scientists (particularly those in academia) aren't enamoured with ELNs, that does not mean that they are not producing digital copies of their scientific research in some form¹⁰. Many researchers make use of simple generic electronic notebooks, such as, OneNote, or even Microsoft Word for capturing their research and importing or linking their data. Further, in our survey on current recording practices, over 80% of our 45 respondents said that they analysed their data and wrote up their work using electronic methods.

For those researchers generating data using computational methods, notebook use is much more sporadic and they are more likely to use scraps of paper to record their thoughts or calculations. However, their methods of preparing, transforming and creating models and simulations still need to be recorded. This includes not just documentation about the intended purpose of the tools, but also ensuring that the code itself is readable, with both readable and sensible variable and function names, most importantly detailed and comprehensible commenting within the code to explain how it works, so that others can verify the code does what it claims to do. Some tools are more effective at providing functionality to support integrated documentation than others. For example, Jupyter Notebooks combine code, data, results and documentation, for those users who make the effort to include it, all within the same document. This makes it possible for others to understand what the author was attempting to do and alter both data and code to see the effects. For workflows it can be much more difficult for someone attempting to reuse the workflow to understand how it works and how it can be altered to achieve a new task.

As we have progressed into a more digital era there has been a growing awareness of the ways in which software and new technologies can improve current workflow practices^{11,12}. However, ELNs are still greatly lacking in the capacity to “combine experimental flexibility with data storage in multiple places” (a direct quote taken from our survey responses), meaning that whilst the use of tools such as Jupyter Notebooks^b are increasingly being used to aid with recording data and code, we are still left with a twofold problem. Firstly that scientists still need to digitise more of their work, and secondly that they need to curate their digital data and records in such a way that they are useable and shareable to others. It is going to be very difficult to achieve the second without the first, and therefore we need to consider different strategies for increasing that level of digitisation, before we can start to consider how to improve it.

^b <https://jupyter.org/>

This has led us to the consideration of how to utilise generic notebooking software in scientific research. As discussed above, lack of usage of ELNs does not necessarily equal not digitising one's work, and it is common for scientists to use tools such as OneNote^c, Microsoft Word^d, Google Docs^e, Evernote^f etc. Rather than trying to move away from that into an ELN that arguably is unlikely to perform the generic notetaking elements as well as these specifically designed pieces of software, we could look to improve their usage and through that start to improve how scientific data and information is recorded and linked together. This could all work together as one Digital Research Notebook (DRN) platform.

Additionally, researchers use an immense range of domain-based software as part of their research lifecycle and these features also need to be taken into account. Therefore, this case study is investigating the user and technical requirements for creating a DRN that interfaces between generic notebooking software and domain-based software, also including the provisions for capturing the metadata and provenance. The mechanics of which are discussed in more detail in Sections 4 & 5.

However, we need to be mindful that providing the right tools is only a part of the story, in order for researchers to want to use them and to gain value from them they need to be usable and need to be focused on the actual goal of the scientists. At Southampton, we have a long history of working with our community to identify both user practices and user requirements for ELNs and data management. We have also investigated how the designs of such interfaces might best support researchers in recording their scientific processes. In Section 2 we discuss how we have made use of our previous research and interaction design methodologies to identify user needs for Digital Research Notebooks and other tools.

^c <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/onenote/digital-note-taking-app>

^d <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/word>

^e <https://docs.google.com/>

^f <https://evernote.com/>

2 User behaviour & user requirements

In order to develop tools that are useful and usable for researchers it is necessary to have an understanding about what their roles are, what they are trying to achieve and how they work. User Experience (UX) design practices are used to help gain an understanding of users, their needs and how the user-facing aspects of a product can be designed to meet those goals. The various resources created through these practices become a tool that can help the stakeholders involved in the development of a product to understand different kinds of users, their backgrounds, frustrations, objectives and desires. These help to elicit specific user requirements and task flows that fit in with the way that users work.

2.1 User Research

There are various ways of conducting user research. At the one end there are user surveys, where behaviours and desires are captured through targeted or random surveying through to detailed interviews, user observations, formal studies, and software pilots to elicit day to day activities and experiences with particular tools, and how different tools may impact user behaviour. At Southampton, we have carried out a range of studies adopting these various different approaches extending back nearly 20 years. Together with our experiences in developing ELNs and other tools for researchers, we have gained significant insights into the needs process recording behaviours and needs of researchers, especially in the chemistry community, but also with other groups such as physicists, computational chemistry, geosciences and archaeology. For disciplines where we have less experience, we can learn about their behaviours and needs from surveys, interviews and literature from others who carry out research in a similar space. For example, some of our colleagues and collaborators elsewhere have investigated electronic notebooks and data sharing across other disciplines such as astronomy and ecology.

2.2 Roles

When developing software, it is important to understand the target audience. Thinking about the various roles that might use the software can help with understanding the goals of such users and the functionality that they will require. There will be at least one kind of user role, but there may well be several. For example, for an ELN used by a department in a business or university there will be researchers creating and utilising notebooks, but there is also likely to be an administrator who is responsible for installing, upgrading and managing the software. Their role may include setting up accounts on the system, managing security and creating back-ups of the data. There may be developers who are responsible for creating extensions to the ELN to enable instruments or an inventory system to be connected. Each user role will have particular tasks they perform or goals that they want to achieve. There is not necessarily a one-to-one match between people and roles. A user who installs a desktop on their own machine are likely to perform multiple roles, and it may be that multiple people fulfil the same role, for example a product may need multiple support technicians.

From our user research in this first stage of the project we have identified ten roles that would be relevant for a DRN and their high-level requirements can be found here: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/roles/>

These include updates of seven previously identified and published roles¹³.

2.3 Personas & Scenarios

Personas are used as a representation of a potential user of a product, and are presented together with some personal information, but primarily information about their skills, goals, concerns, and motivations. Personas are usually fictitious users with imaginary personal details, but they are meant to be realistic archetypes of actual users based upon research about and discussions with actual future users of the system. These can be used to facilitate a common understanding of what the user wants to achieve and what they are able to do. They can become very helpful when discussing functionality in the proposed product because it is easier to talk about a user with a known background, frustrations and goals and what they might find useful or how they might feel about a particular feature. The following is an example persona (Figure 1) showing role and background information, technical skills, goals, drivers, and frustrations.

Name: Guy	Occupation: Professor Role: Supervisor Site: City University	Area: Organic Chemistry and Open Science
	Bio: Professor Guy and his students conduct research into developing ways to build molecules & to develop drugs to help treat tropical diseases. Guy fosters relationships with collaborators across the world and is always looking for ways to engage new collaborators and share research. He believes strongly in the value of open science and collaboration to share techniques and speed up the process of drug discovery.	
Technology	Goals: Develop & refine new techniques to make molecules Encourage and manage members of his research team Share the techniques and research findings of the group Identify new projects and engage new collaborators Effectively manage new research projects and collaborators	
Internet	Drivers: Developing better techniques Encourage research sharing and collaboration Demonstrating and improving effectiveness of open science	
Software		
Mobile Apps		
Data Management		
Metadata		
Programming		
	Frustrations: Methods & data inaccessible in paper archives Difficulty searching for relevant data by chemical structure Difficult to identify and engage with potential collaborators	

Figure 1: Example persona within organic chemistry

A scenario is a narrative description of how one or more personas might interact with and use a tool to achieve their goals. Scenarios can be used to elicit information about the requirements for digital tools and inform ideas about the kinds of interfaces that would be most effective in the contexts and environments of use. Scenarios can help developers to understand what user's motivations are to use a tool and how they might go about using it. They can also begin to refine the tasks that the user needs to complete in order to achieve their goals.

Personas are usually used in conjunction with scenarios and storyboards in which they can be used in combination to explore the relationship between different roles and the flow of information between roles and different parts of a system.

For the first part of the project, we have expanded on four scenarios and sets of personas from our research with chemists that we previously published¹³ and added a new scenario and set of

personas for research in astronomy and for geosciences to cover a broader range of behaviours and needs within physical sciences.

The 6 scenarios together with their personas can be found at the following links:

- Astronomy:
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/astronomy/#scenario>
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/astronomy/#personas>
- Environmental Chemistry – Closed Research Including Interaction with a Funding Body:
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-1/#scenario>
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-1/#personas>
- Organic Chemistry - Fully Open Research Including Interaction with Global Scientific Collaborators:
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-2/#scenario>
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-2/#personas>
- Synthetic Chemistry - Closed Research in a Local Research Group:
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-3/#scenario>
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-3/#personas>
- Chemistry - Undergraduate Practical Course:
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-4/#scenario>
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-4/#personas>
- Geosciences:
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/geosciences/#scenario>
 - <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/geosciences/#personas>

2.4 Data Path Swim Lanes

A swim lane diagram is a form of flowchart originally used to describe business processes, that visually show how a process works, including the people involved and the flow of information between these roles or within the system. The swim lane tracks the high-level steps of the process and the actions of different roles to cause the capture or movement of information in the system. Swim lanes can be used to illustrate the flow of information, the key roles involved in the flow, elicit the current user experience, identify knowledge gaps and identify areas where the process could be improved. In UX they often include other information, such as users' emotions or attitudes to their experience when following a process, for example using a website to carry out a particular task. This visually represents very clearly where in the process users are struggling with some aspect of the website or other tool.

A concern for us has been how to represent the flow of different kinds of information for scientists carrying out their research and recording their process. In particular, how information flows and is transformed from planning to publication, and what metadata could be captured along the way. For this first stage of the project, we have developed a novel swim lane diagram (see Figure 2) to visually display and capture these information flows, along with the user roles and user experience. These swim lanes largely cover the processes as they are now, rather than exploring how they could be with the development of new or improved tools for researchers.

The Data Path Swim Lanes contain horizontal lanes to display different information. The first is a 'cartoon' storyboard featuring the different personas from the scenario and a high-level process or processes that they are carrying out. This storyboard shows the steps they are taking,

the interactions they are having with various tools, and the flow of information between them and others.

In the next swim lane, the very high-level actions or tasks are captured, for example plan project, search data interpret data, share data, approve plan, write report and so on. The next swim lane details the various tools that the personas are using in that part of the storyboard, including the ELN/DRN, external tools, software and systems, and paper notebooks or other documents. The next swim lane details any data and types of data, metadata and provenance information that is produced at this stage in the task.

The next two swim lanes deal with the data lifecycle. The first of these provides a visual representation of the life cycle activities being carried out at this stage of the task in the storyboard. It is not necessarily the case that researchers would follow the steps of the research data lifecycle one after the other in the order expected. Often the iterative nature of data collection and analysis followed by more data collection means that some processes are revisited. The stages included are Plan & Design, Collect, Document, Process, Analyse, Store (Local), Publish, Preserve, Discover and Reuse. The next swim lane records what the data that is captured or manipulated in that stage is being used for, in particular whether it is for local reuse or being produced to share with others, and whether knowledge is being produced.

Figure 2 shows an example data path swim lane from one of the chemistry scenarios. Full data Paths for the various scenarios can be found at the following links:

- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/astronomy/#data-paths>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-1/#data-paths>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-2/#data-paths>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-3/#data-paths>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/geosciences/#data-paths>

Figure 2: Example of a completed data path swim lane diagram

2.5 Storyboards

Storyboarding is a useful way to transform scenarios and personas into a format that can help to develop specifications for new tools, by providing examples of how tools might be used, and what they might be used to accomplish. Storyboards provide a narrative of an everyday interaction between the users and the tool, based on the personas and scenarios that have been developed for a product. Storyboards can help to highlight features that would provide a significant benefit to users, including those that may not have previously been considered, in addition to handling user expectations about more obvious tasks. Storyboards are more usually used to visually describe how a new tool may function, but they are also a useful tool for communicating current processes (and serve as a basis for the Data Path Swim Lane above).

The following is an example of a storyboard exploring potential functionality of a DRN based on the needs of personas from one of the chemistry scenarios.

Figure 3: A Storyboard exploring the potential different types of functionality from a DRN

Links to Storyboards for the various Scenarios can be found at the following links:

- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/astronomy/#storyboards>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-1/#storyboards>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-2/#storyboards>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-3/#storyboards>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/chemistry-4/#storyboards>
- <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/geosciences/#storyboards>

2.6 User stories

User stories express in simple terms the goals of particular type of user, and can be used to explore the functionality a system should provide. and the value that the functionality will provide to users. The user stories are written from the perspective of the users of the system and facilitate communication within the software development team and stakeholders and are based upon the scenarios, personas, storyboards and other assets that describe what the users are trying to achieve. User stories are a helpful way to identify broad requirements and quickly prioritise them through discussions with stakeholders. User stories are not system requirements as such and do not necessarily match one to one with product features, it may be that functionality provided by the product enables a user to achieve multiple goals as specified by user stories, or that more complex functionality needs to be developed to address a single user story. For example, the ability to add an image and a data file to a notebook can be addressed by enabling a user to add multiple kinds of file, whereas enabling the user to perform a structure search in the notebook requires a number of different features such as functionality to draw a chemical, search by name, search by material codes, perform some filtering of search results, display search results and so on. One way of dealing with user stories that map to large-scale or complex functionality like this is to break them down into smaller stories. The simple basic nature of the user stories means that they need to be expanded to add detail and background through further discussion.

Almost two hundred user stories have been identified across the following fourteen categories:

- Generic requirements
- Administration
- Creating and managing plans
- Running and recording the experiment / study
- Chemistry specific requirements
- Geosciences specific requirements
- Adding and viewing metadata
- Integrating with other systems
- Integrating with literature sources
- Writing up and publishing
- Preserving the work
- Team management
- Activity tracking & social media
- Teaching

All the User stories identified from the user assets can be found at the following link:

<https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-stories/>

2.7 User Flows

A user flow represents the user's journey to complete a specific task and expands on the user stories by exploring how they link together to help the user to achieve a very high-level goal. Three user flows have been created to describe the user's journey through related high-level tasks to represent important common behaviour between researchers in the chemistry

scenarios. The first two describe the process typically used to plan, create and record a chemistry experiment, beginning with searching for a chemical structure so that appropriate protocols for the experiment can be discovered and imported into the notebook to support the researcher. The first user flow describes the process of capture and recording the experiment when the researcher performs their own analysis of the materials produced by the experiment. The second flow describes an example of the process if the researcher sends their sample to a specialist centre or service for the analysis, such as the National Crystallography Service. The third user flow describes the process for publishing the results of the experiment to a database or journal, for example the Royal Society of Chemistry's Synthetic Pages.

These user flows have been captured as both graphical and textual forms as they provide complementary ways of presenting the same information. The graphical version provides an easy-to-read visual version of the task flow, enabling different paths to be represented and focuses only on the actions that the user or another actor performs. The Text form version provides additional information about what the user sees, what the system does, and what metadata is captured and utilized at each step. The following shows an example of part of User Flow 2.

Figure 4: Excerpts from graphical depiction of user flow 2 – Analysis as a service

Both kinds of user flows can be found at the following links:

- User Flow 1 – Graphical version: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-flows-graphic-format/#UF1>
- User Flow 1 – Text version: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-flows-text-format/#UF1>
- User Flow 2 – Graphical version: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-flows-graphic-format/#UF2>
- User Flow 2 – Text version: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-flows-text-format/#UF2>
- User Flow 3 – Graphical version: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-flows-graphic-format/#UF3>
- User Flow 3 – Text version: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/user-flows-text-format/#UF3>

2.8 User Interface Designs

One of the clearest ways to enable development teams and users to visualise a tool and to understand the potential ways that users will use the tool is through the creation of prototype interfaces. Prototypes can be useful to demonstrate the capabilities of the system and to generate feedback that can help to fine-tune the design. Prototypes enable different design ideas to be trialled before spending time and resources on developing the actual tool, including trying out alternative flows and designs. Prototypes can be built at different levels of complexity and interaction, from the very simplest paper prototype to high-fidelity prototypes that are almost final versions of the software that can be used for formal usability testing later in the process. Low-fidelity prototypes can be quickly changed, especially under testing where any problems identified can be rapidly changed and the new design tested for effectiveness.

For this stage in the project, the user interface prototypes have been designed to help explore the functionality that can be provided and how the user flows can be supported through different aspects of the interface. Prospective user interface designs have been produced for each of the three user flows described above. The designs for each user flow have been linked together as a flow to show how different interface 'screens' link together as the user might use them. The following shows part of the user interface flow for User Flow 2 and shows examples of developed interface designs and placeholders for screens that are not required to be developed in more detail at this stage.

Figure 5: Example of user interface flow design from user flow 2

Links to user prospective interface designs for the three user flows can be found at the following links:

- User Flow 1: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/ui-uf1/>
- User Flow 2: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/ui-uf2/>
- User Flow 3: <https://www.psd.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/ui-uf3/>

2.9 Conclusions and Next steps

Examining user behaviour from different kinds of scientists is important to understand what are common behaviours and what are likely to be specific to certain disciplines. Within science there are many common behaviours and goals. We all carry out experiments and studies of different kinds to acquire data and to make discoveries. We need to record the processes that we follow to help us remember what we did and to enable what we did to be repeated by ourselves and others. We also need to share our methods and results with others so that we can effectively communicate our discoveries and enable others to build their work upon our findings. This sharing may only occur within a single team or organisation within industry, but for many it also involves sharing the findings with the broader scientific community and even potentially the

public. These common behaviours and goals mean that at a high level we can develop tools to support these actions and goals. We need access to information that others have shared and published in order to create our plans and select our methods. We need to be able to capture and record what we do and what we observe. We also need to have mechanisms to communicate that information, and that ranges from through local peer review by a manager, supervisor or team member, through to publication for the benefit of the community.

Technology and tools have the opportunity to reduce the burden of work on the users. As we learn from looking at different ways that researchers currently record their experiments, such as the examples below in Figure 6 and Figure 7, there does not need to be just one tool or one solution that works for everyone from each discipline. However, we can develop tools that add significant value for users by providing appropriate integrations to reduce duplication and screen switching, adding additional functionality, and automating tasks that would otherwise need to be done manually.

Figure 6: Storyboard exploring experiment recording in a paper notebook

Figure 7: Storyboard exploring experiment recording using Word & Excel

These and other examples of how researchers record their experiments are from¹⁴ and can also be found at the this link: <https://www.psdi.ac.uk/case-study-6/resources/different-ways-to-record/>

Extending our exploration of user behaviour has helped to identify the roles of users who would want to use the tools in this space, and also identified changes that are happening within science. Rather than the lone scientist running their experiments and creating and analysing their own data, it is increasingly common for the experiment process to be spread across multiple groups and organisations, with potentially different researchers collecting, processing, analysing, and publishing the data. It is clear that data is flowing between multiple systems and technologies. Data is used in the planning of experiments, and many scientists are creating new results and findings from data they had no part in collecting. Some kind of broader oversight is required to manage this data flow, reflected in the value of a data manager to ensure the use of standards and to make sure data is properly managed and stored. Once the research extends beyond the single researcher model, recording the experiment (only) in a paper notebook is no longer sufficient to ensure that the experiment record – the ‘process’ - is not detached from the data however it is used.

The various scenarios, personas and data path swim lanes tease out the assorted ways that different researchers work with research data and their varied goals and needs. They also help to identify other functionality that could add value to digital notebook or digital research management tools we may develop that go beyond the more obvious text-editing and data linking functionality expected with current ELNs. For example:

- ability to connect data sources and extract content that can be used to automatically populate a plan, safety information, and reference information for an experiment;
- capture and extract provenance information from data, code, protocols, literature and other data sources so that the provenance trail for new results and publications includes information about reuse and recognition;
- ability to automatically generate a curated package from selected experiment records and associated assets for preservation and sharing;
- enable approvals/auditing/peer review to be configured for those teams where it is required, for example plans, safety information, and completed experiments;
- use a DRN as a tool for project management, team management and cross project collaboration;
- use a DRN as a tool for knowledge management, knowledge sharing and discussion;
- use a DRN as a tool to facilitate teaching;
- ability to connect physical and digital systems for process and sample recording.

For future phases of the project more work can be done on exploring user behaviour and requirements. In particular, more investigation is needed into user behaviour and requirements for researchers working with primarily computer-based research such as high performing computing and workflows. From this more user research and user experience assets such as the data path swim lanes, storyboards and interface designs.

For developing accurate user interfaces for testing, it would also be valuable to have a thorough investigation of the metadata provided and required by various services that would be desired for a Digital Research Notebook to interact with, and what benefits and capabilities these different services can provide for users.

Creating interactive prototypes for different communities based on appropriate scenarios, personas, data paths, storyboards and user flows would demonstrate the capabilities of being able to tailor the notebook based upon the services and metadata that are appropriate to those communities.

3 User Survey & Landscape Assessment

Over the last two decades we have seen slow and steady progress towards further digitisation. Computing power has increased, and mobile devices such as phones and tablets are substantially more powerful for use in a working setting. There has been a growing awareness that scientific research should be digitised and as such more research has been undertaken into understanding how best to use digital tools to support this effort. However, nothing has had as much potential to disrupt and change scientific working practices than the global pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent lockdowns turned almost everybody's working practices and day to day working routine upside down. For many, going into work, sharing physical copies of data/notes and indeed at times accessing the laboratory simply wasn't an option. However, how much did this really change things in terms of digitisation, and will these changes remain now that the world is getting back to a "new normal".

We conducted a survey designed to understand scientists current working practices, to see how (if at all) things had changed since the pandemic. We used the research conducted by Kanza et al in 2017⁷ as the basis for the survey design, such that we could ask some similar questions and facilitate comparisons. In addition, we identified a few new areas of investigation where questions were required. The full list of survey questions and details about the survey duration and participants can be found in Appendix B. The questions related to structure were included for Case Study 8: The Role of Structure in Physical Sciences Data Management and will be discussed in their report.

We also used the format of the ELN Landscape Assessment undertaken in Kanza et al⁷ and updated it to reflect the current status of the ELN Market. The full results of this can be found in Appendix C.

3.1 Current use of paper and electronic devices

Back in 2017, the responses from the research conducted by Kanza et al⁷ demonstrated that researchers work in very different ways with different working patterns, and that they use a mix of paper and electronic methods to record their work depending on the task at hand. In the PSDI survey we asked our respondents a similar question, and the results are displayed below in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Results from Q1 regarding use of paper and electronic device in process recording

Overall, we can still draw the same conclusions as 5 years ago based on this data. One thing that has changed, is that there is a reduction in those who are purely using paper, which is a step in right direction. However, the overall split of the use of paper/electronic methods to record scientific research remains similar with respect to the different activities. Computational methods are still heavily relied upon at the intermediary and final stages of work, e.g., data analysis and writeup. However, the planning stages and recording data during experiments still remain quite split between the use of paper and electronic methods, and it is clear that even now scientists still use paper-based methods quite frequently in these situations. This isn't entirely surprising as the laboratory was always considered the most difficult location in which to record notes purely in an electronic form, due to all of the barriers to adoption that were detailed in Section 1.2.1.1. This suggests that whilst things are shifting slowly, there is still much work to be done in providing suitable tools for those earlier stages in the research lifecycle.

3.2 Organising and Linking together Work

In addition to using a mixture of different methods to record their work, our previous research also demonstrated that scientists organise and link their work together in very different ways. Shankar's studies in 2007¹⁵ concluded that taking notes and creating a standard method of data entry was personal to different scientists and Kanza et al's 2017 studies⁷ demonstrated that this also holds true for organisational methods. In 2017, the study by Kanza et al showed that scientists took different organisational strategies for paper and electronic notes, and used a variety of methods to link together paper and electronic notes, including using dates, codes, and adding hyperlinks of file paths into paper lab books. The user study participants described using a number of software packages to organise, and link together their work. Cloud storage tools such as Google Drive and Dropbox were mentioned with respect to having work all stored in one place. Additionally, some organisational tools were mentioned such as keep notes and google tasks.

If we fast forward to today, our survey respondents were asked exactly the same question, "How is your work organised and linked together". The results of these responses are categorised in

Figure 9, and show a level of similarity in approach to previous responses, but demonstrate an increase in both the use of software and range of software tools being used.

Figure 9: Categorized responses to questions about linking and organising work

In terms of organising and linking research together between paper and electronic, there was not a significant change. There is still a clear habit of using a linking piece of information to bridge between the two systems. The use of hyperlinks and filepaths directly into paper lab notebooks shows that there is still a pattern of having paper notes linked to electronic data, and these links are being used to help the users find these related but disparate data sources.

Additionally, there remains a clear pattern of using unique ids for experiments and projects and using these to signify which notes belong to which, both in the electronic and paper note systems. Unfortunately, the necessity to produce these between paper and electronic systems suggest that there are still portions of the scientific record that exist solely on paper. This leads back to the first stage of the remaining problem that “scientists need to digitise more of their work”.

In terms of how they electronically organise and link their work, there is an obvious increase in the number of software packages used, including notably the use of software specifically for organisation. Figure 9 shows categories of software that were noted by respondents with respect to organising and linking their work. This overall increase in the use of software will be discussed in further detail in the following section.

3.3 Use of Software

The results of Kanza et al's 2017 study⁷ concluded that despite some scientists preferring paper notebooks, they still frequently use a wide range of digital technology in their work. There are a number of generic notebook tools or even word processors available that can be used to capture the day-to-day scientific process. This has been a common theme in the past two sections with most participants citing the use of electronic methods for different aspects of their work.

3.3.1 Notebooking Software

We asked our participants about what types of software tools they used, what software tools they used for data sharing and whether they used a Digital Research Notebook. We deliberately left this question open to interpretation of the meaning of 'digital research notebook' to see the range of responses that we would get. 55% said yes, they used a DRN and 45% said no. The word cloud in Figure 10 shows the range of responses given by those respondents who said yes.

Figure 10: Word cloud depiction of the responses to Q8 regarding use of digital research notebooks

With respect to the use of 'Digital Research Notebooks' as interpreted by our respondents, most of the answers given were not Electronic Lab Notebooks. A few participants are using them, Lab Archives^g, RSpace^h and Biovia Workbookⁱ were mentioned. However, the majority of the software mentioned was more generic note booking software such as Microsoft Word, Google Docs, Zim^j, Overleaf^k, Evernote etc. Further, there was a clear preference for OneNote and Jupyter Notebooks.

^g <https://www.labarchives.com/>

^h <https://www.researchspace.com/>

ⁱ <https://www.3ds.com/products-services/biovia/products/laboratory-informatics/electronic-lab-notebooks/biovia-workbook/>

^j <https://zim-wiki.org/>

^k <https://www.overleaf.com/>

3.3.2 Data Sharing Software

Similarly, we asked our participants about what software they used to share their data and very few of the results were ELNs. The different categories of software identified are shown below in Figure 11.

<p><u>Communication</u> MS Teams Jitsi Discord Slack Zoom Skype Mattermost</p>	<p><u>Organisation / Decision making</u> Notion Mural MS Teams Asana</p>	<p><u>Domain software (structures)</u> Avogadro Chemoffice Diamond Mercury</p>
<p><u>Notetaking</u> Google Docs Lyx Word OneNote Overleaf Notion</p>	<p><u>ELNs</u> CDD Science Cloud Lab Archives</p>	<p><u>Data Analysis</u> Spreadsheets Origin</p>
<p><u>Code</u> Bash scripts Python routines Mercurial Git(hub) Gitlab Bitbucket*</p>	<p><u>Cloud Storage</u> Sharepoint/ OneDrive MS Teams Dedicated Cloud Dropbox Google Drive</p>	<p><u>Bespoke software</u></p>

Figure 11: Categorized software responses for collaboration / sharing. All identified from Q9 except * from Q11

This again exemplifies that the lack of use of ELNs does not mean a lack of use of software. Further, clearly the participants want features that aren't necessarily provided by an ELN. It is not surprising that there has been a surge in the use of communication software as the COVID-19 pandemic made that a necessity.

When we asked our participants about what had changed since COVID-19 some participants mentions that there was an increase in digital sharing using cloud software, which again is unsurprising. MS Teams^l/ OneNote / Sharepoint^m is clearly more in use than in our earlier studies as MS Teams only came into existence in 2017 (with a free version in 2018). In combination with Google Drive not adhering to the European Economic Area (EEA) requirements and many universities purchasing office 365 subscriptions, this has meant a significant shift to the use of the Microsoft suite, although many still use other programs alongside that.

The use of software and scripts to share code has also increased as there has been greater emphasis on making these scripts available. Some domain-based software packages are also

^l <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software>

^m <https://www.microsoft.com/en-gb/microsoft-365/sharepoint/collaboration>

used for data sharing. This is almost certainly due to some data / work requiring specialist software to handle certain data types. This will be discussed further in the next section.

3.3.3 Other Software

Earlier studies also elicited that there is a wealth of domain-based software available for the physical sciences. Kanza (2018)¹⁶ conducted a study to ascertain what software packages existed in the domain of Chemistry and how much they were used.

In our PSDI survey we asked our participants what other software they used in their work. Over 200 different types of software were mentioned. We categorised the different types of software, using both the categories identified in Kanza (2018)¹⁶ and identified some additional categories that emerged from the data as the initial set of categories had only been designed for chemistry software. The full list can be found in Appendix D.

Table 2 - Categorised responses from PSDI question on 'use of other software'

Category	Totals (/206)	Percentage
Crystallographic Software	26	12.44%
Coding Software	22	10.53%
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	22	10.53%
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	21	10.05%
Data Visualisation & Analysis	19	9.09%
General document processing	18	8.61%
Other	13	6.22%
Spectroscopic Software	10	4.78%
Image processing Software	9	4.31%
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	8	3.83%
Organisational Software	7	3.35%
Chemistry Bibliographic Databases	5	2.39%
Database Software	5	2.39%
Instrument Control	5	2.39%
Simulation (non-chemical)	5	2.39%
Communication Software	4	1.91%
Molecular Editor Software	3	1.44%
Nanostructures Modelling Software	2	0.96%
Machine Learning	2	0.96%
CAD Software	2	0.96%
Workflow software	1	0.48%

As demonstrated by Table 2, there are a great deal of different types of software that are being used across the physical sciences community, both generic and domain specific. Similarly, to above, none of these pieces of software are ELNs; and whilst some of the features provided by these different software packages exist in some ELNs, overall, it demonstrates a desire for a much wider range of features than an ELN would offer. This further emphasises that there is a highly personalised need for access to many different domain-based features.

Further, we investigated what domains were represented by the wide array of ELN software that is currently available. There are dozens of Electronic Laboratory Notebooks currently available, many of which are highly tailored to particular disciplinary specialisations as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Discipline specialisations within current ELNs

This again demonstrates that scientists have a very diverse set of needs when it comes to using digital tools and it is increasingly unlikely that there will ever be one tool that encompasses all of these features, so we need to figure out how to make what we have work better together and to address the second problem 'improving data and record curation'. This needs to be taken into account when proposing any new solution.

3.4 Barriers and Limitations

Previous research highlighted the barriers to adoption and limitations of ELNs. However, with the wide use of other types of software we wanted to understand what barriers are currently in place, with the optimistic outlook that the new working practices many will have had to adopt as a result of COVID-19 might have accelerated some progress in this area.

We asked our participants about whether they encountered any restrictions in trying to share their data, and about what barriers or limitations they faced that would prevent their research from reaching its full potential. There are a wealth of barriers and concerns that range from cost, hardware and software issues, problems with current systems, and people themselves. These have been grouped and described below.

3.4.1 Logistical Barriers

- **Cost:** This is pretty much always listed as a barrier, and is an ongoing issue. Researchers face issues with respect to lack of funding, or running projects on small budgets. This is then further exacerbated by the cost of conducting the research, such as cost for software packages and open access publication fees. It is obvious that any DRN would need to work with existing software that researchers already had access to via their institutions or open-source software.
- **Time:** Whilst this is a hard problem to solve, time is a constant barrier, particularly in an ever increasingly busy world. This isn't just lack of time itself with respect to having too many projects to work on, it is also the time it takes to use some systems, the time to find

and exploit data and to convert it between systems. One of the many reasons that scientists don't digitise all of their work, or why they don't digitise it to its full potential is the time cost and the fact that the current systems in place would make this a very arduous task.

3.4.2 People Barriers

- **Attitude:** The road to digitisation is a socio-technical task. In order to make improvements in this area we need the support of the users. People are often afraid of change and it can be very challenging to persuade an entire research group to adopt a new piece of software. There can also often be an unwillingness to share data and therefore an unwillingness to put the data in a format where it can be easily found, accessed and used.
- **Training:** There will be a need for training to learn any new system, and researchers need to be adequately trained to manage their data well and digitise their work appropriately. If they haven't done it before then it's not something they are going to learn overnight, and given the wealth of poorly digitised data, clearly further education is required in this area.

3.4.3 Data Barriers

- **(Un) FAIR Data:** Another key barrier researchers are facing is how much data doesn't adhere to FAIR standards. There are issues relating to finding the data researchers need in the first place, both in terms of being able to discover it full stop or locate it via references if they are incorrect. Accessibility is also an issue as often the data cannot be accessed due to embargos. Interoperability remains a huge problem as there are too many different data formats and conventions, and some data is only available in proprietary formats. Researchers have also cited that it is currently a very time-consuming endeavour to make data FAIR, which produces a circular issue.
- **Metadata & Provenance:** Metadata has been mentioned a lot by our respondents. It's hard to capture metadata and often researchers don't, or at least they don't record useful metadata which then means that data often lacks context. Being able to trace the source of the data is very important to researchers but often the original data is not made available, and there is a lack of appropriate historic data, making it hard to understand the origin of many experiments and papers.
- **Size of Data:** Some of our participants mentioned that the size of the data they work with is an issue. Dealing with large datasets is a challenge as is sharing them. There are a limited number of places to store large datasets and their size causes issues with uploads/downloads and collaboration.

3.4.4 Hardware & Software Barriers

- **Storage:** Data storage options have been cited as another barrier. Many universities provide Office 365 accounts and storage options. However, this clearly does not occur for all institutions as lack of cloud storage, limited data storage and poor cloud storage options have all been cited as limitations.
- **Software:** Software was raised as a huge problem for researchers for many different reasons. There is a call for more modern software, as many participants are still using outdated software that also lacks proper documentation. A notable quote from one of our participants was "There is no ELN that combines experimental flexibility with data storage in multiple places". There are also issues with system and software compatibility,

for example trying to use Teams on Linux. Lots of software still only works for either Windows, or Windows and Mac. Additionally, a lot of software programs that researchers need to use don't work well with one another.

- **Hardware:** A lot of scientific laboratories need an equipment overhaul. They are often full of legacy equipment that only works with certain older operating systems or machines, and often uses outdated data formats. This is a key aspect that needs to be addressed if we are to improve the digital scientific record.

This demonstrates that while some of our participants did say that they had seen a greater shift to the use of digital technologies since COVID-19, many barriers still remain to be overcome with respect to the current ways of conducting scientific research.

3.5 Survey Conclusions

Overall, this survey demonstrates that we still do not have a viable solution for the improvement of the digitisation of scientific research/ One of the main aims of this survey was to find out if the COVID-19 pandemic had brought about any significant changes, as the lockdowns necessitated many people having to significantly change their working patterns and habits. Given the general requirements to work from home and communicate via online methods, we hypothesised that this must have had a powerful impact on the digitisation of work, and the use of digital tools to achieve this. This has occurred in some ways, although not perhaps in the way that we expected.

We posed the question to our participants: "Since the COVID-19 pandemic have you changed your research methods with respect to recording and sharing your work? If so, what aspects are digital that didn't used to be?" and received some mixed answers. Some participants said nothing had changed; some participants said that they had increased their use of digital technologies but that this was something they had already started putting into practice before COVID-19. Some said that there had been a change and that more of their work was digital, but it's worth noting that less than 10% mentioned the use of an ELN as part of this. Most participants who cited a change noted that they had more data in a digital format, or that they were putting more effort into versioning work and syncing files between work and home computers. A more significant change was the not unexpected increase in the use of virtual technologies to accommodate meetings, or the use of more note taking and organisational software to manage their work.

It appears that COVID-19 has led to a level of further use of digital tools to communicate, digitise work and share data in an electronic form. However, this has not changed anything with the respect to ELN adoption. It is clear from this question and also the results detailed above that whilst scientists have looked to other software to aid their research process, this has been in the form of either generic software to enable notes, task management, literature linking and supporting the use of code, or they have looked to domain-based software for specific solutions pertaining to their research.

We have used the research conducted as part of this case study, alongside the data gathered in all of our historic studies to identify a number of features that are obviously required by the physical sciences community. These will be discussed in more detail in Section 4.

4 Features

The combination of our previous research and the conclusions that we have made as part of our survey analysis have reinforced the view that there is no simple solution to creating a tool to digitise scientific research, and that a future solution simply will not be eventually creating the 'right' ELN that every scientist will want to use. Not only do scientists still not really like the idea of ELNs, the physical sciences are such a diverse wide-ranging set of disciplines that it would be close to impossible to capture all of the features required in one piece of software. Therefore, rather than focus on the creation of a new piece of software we have outlined all of the key features that are required by the physical sciences community, and then in Section 5 we will discuss potential technical methods of implementing these using existing tools.

4.1 Required Features

In previous research by Kanza et al⁷, similar studies were conducted to identify the range of features that a scientist would want from an Electronic Lab Notebook. This was explored through the medium of a layered approach. As shown in Figure 13 this comprises of 3 layers; the Notebook Layer, the Domain Layer and the Semantic Layer.

Figure 13: Layers of features previously raised by Kanza⁷

However, having continued this research it has become clear that even though this was working along the right lines, this approach isn't entirely appropriate. It is obvious from our research that even more features are required than initially identified. Scientists want generic notebooking features, but they also want the features that are afforded by a range of other software including

both domain-based software and other types of useful software such as referencing and organisational software. There is also a high requirement for supporting FAIR data and offering a wide range of data management tools. A fair amount of these features exist in different software packages, although some still require creation or refinement. We propose that the best way of addressing these needs would be to use a modular approach. This means that rather than reinventing the wheel, we would identify the different software programs that already offer some of the required features and work to enable them to interface with one another. The outstanding features could then be created.

We collated together all the required features that were identified throughout the last decade of research and categorised them. Figure 14 shows how we envisage a DRN system working with PSDI Core to incorporate these features.

We are going to describe the functionality of the high-level categories for the features (represented by nodes on the diagram) identified in Figure 14 and note which ones would look to be facilitated by existing software. The full breakdown of the individual features for each category can be found in Appendix E.

Figure 14: Example of all the features of a DRN system, demonstrating PSDI Core interfacing with different services and features

4.1.1 Generic Features

There are several desired features for the high-level characteristics of a DRN.

- **API Access:** A DRN should be accessible via an API (Application Programming Interface).
- **Automation:** Users want a certain level of automation, with files saving and syncing automatically, automatic updates, automatic extraction of metadata etc.
- **General Features:** Users want a DRN to be simple, scalable, transparent and enable them to access all their work in one place.
- **GUI:** Users want a graphical user interface to work with so they don't have to understand the inner workings of a DRN to use it.
- **Localisation:** Users want to be able to use a DRN in their own language working on their own timezones.
- **Remote Access:** Users want to be able to access a DRN remotely from other devices.
- **Synchronisation:** Users want to be able to work synchronously and edit / work on multiple documents / datasets at once.

4.1.2 Notebooking Features

There are a number of desired features that either exist as part of generic notebooking software or would naturally extend onto notebooking software.

- **Content Support:** Scientists want to be able to record and write up their work using a wide range of different content types (e.g., free text, numbers, photos, diagrams, graphs etc – the full list can be found in Appendix E). A majority of these will be part and parcel of using generic notebooking software such as OneNote.
- **Interaction and Access:** In addition to supporting interfacing with paper, scientists want to be able to interact with a DRN in multiple ways including handwritten notes, using digital pens, via voice etc. A DRN should also be accessible via a range of devices including mobile phones and tablets, and be available offline.
- **Link to other files:** Some files might exist that are too large to incorporate in a document or set of notes e.g., large datasets or code scripts. In this instance users need to be able to link to these external files.
- **Organisation / Reconfiguration:** Users want to be able to organise and reconfigure their work, so it can be re-ordered to be viewed by person, experiment, date etc.
- **Paper Integration:** A big reason why scientists still don't digitise all of their work is due to the affordances of paper. Paper still remains easier to scribble notes on, and for many it remains the natural easy way of making notes. Even through a global pandemic this hasn't changed, scientists still make notes on paper and the ones they deem important enough will make it into an electronic format. We need to ascertain the current methods of interfacing with paper (e.g., hybrid devices, scanning paper notes) and ensure that these are available for users. Innovation on extracting information from unstructured data e.g., paper records, images and annotated charts is currently being undertaken by researchers, including members of the Frey group at the University of Southampton working on the Data Revival projectⁿ. This includes creating chemistry-based contextualisation around extracted chemical names, formulas and chemical structures.
- **Referencing & Literature:** Scientists want access to literature via their DRN. In some senses these features are covered by referencing software as they require the capability

ⁿ <https://labs.futureworlds.com/data-revival/>

to link to literature and cite literature sources. However, there is also a deeper requirement to be able to extract data from legacy literature, and import/export literature references directly from a DRN. Users also want to be able to cite data and code in their work.

- **Word Processing:** One of the reasons that scientists continue to use software such as Microsoft Word and OneNote to record their notes is due to their superior word processing capabilities. Our ELN landscape assessment concluded the most widely supported file formats for including in the ELN are Microsoft Excel and Word, and often the ELN is able to process these files to convert them to the ELN format or enable the user to edit the content within the ELN, A DRN platform should interface with existing notebooking software such as these programs in a similar fashion.

4.1.3 Data Features

Data is at the cornerstone of scientific research, and as the amount of data generated (predominantly electronically but sometimes not) increases, researchers have ever growing needs for different digital tools to manage their data.

- **API Access:** A DRN should interface with APIs so users can extract the data they need.
- **Data Access:** There needs to be the concept of different access control levels with different user permissions. This is common with a lot of the software that would be integrated to create a DRN, but needs to be taken into account for any new features or programs that don't currently facilitate this ability.
- **Data Conversion:** This is a key feature required by scientists. Given the plethora of different data formats available for representing data in the physical sciences, and given how many pieces of software use different formats and potentially only facilitate import/export in certain formats, the capability to convert between formats is vital. There is no universal format converter for the physical sciences, so existing tools would need to be considered and a new one developed to enable this feature.
- **Data Exchange:** A DRN should facilitate data exchange, this may be through a data exchange platform.
- **Data Integration:** Scientists often need to integrate datasets; they need tools to enable the collation and integration of data.
- **Data Management:** Poor data management is one of the major issues with the current state of digitisation of physical sciences research. Scientists need a platform to record, manage and curate their data.
- **Data Quality:** Users need to be able to quality check their data, and there needs to be the notion of categorising data as "trusted".
- **Data Retention:** Data needs to be preserved for the required period of time, and there also needs to be a mechanism to remove obsolete data.
- **Data Security:** Any DRN would need to be offer secure storage, backup and archiving features.
- **Data Standards:** Standards are a key issue with respect to digitising scientific research. Ideally a DRN would be configured to work with required domain data standards, and would have features to ensure data integrity and consistent use of standards. This realistically means that we still have a requirement for standardised file formats that work across different domains and pieces of software.
- **Data Support:** A DRN should support data from other resources, and be able to deal with all different stages of data.

- **FAIR Data:** A DRN should support curating data to ensure it is FAIR, and publishing FAIR data.
- **Identifiers:** The use of identifiers is very important, not just for data but for all aspects of scientific research. A DRN would need to be able to link data together using standard identifiers (e.g., chemical identifiers) in addition to working with unique IDs for samples, experiments, researchers etc.
- **Provenance:** A DRN should contain or link to tools to capture provenance. Users want to be able to capture the provenance of their data, code and structures. Users also want to be able to see the algorithms/code that were used to create data or perform data analysis. It is also important to users to be able to track what happens to their work, it would be useful to be able to see what datasets and work get re-used and how.

4.1.4 Publishing & Sharing Features

One of the desired end products of a scientific research project is creating publications. Users want a DRN that will aid with this process:

- **Documentation & Instructions:** One of the key aspects of recording your work (in any fashion) is to document your work and provide instructions to others as to how to implement it or use it. A DRN needs to facilitate this.
- **DOIs:** We need better mechanisms to create and supply DOIs / permanent links for data.
- **Export:** Users want to be able to export all aspects of their work (including the entire notebook) in multiple formats.
- **Licensing:** There is a requirement to be able to create license for data, code and research prior to sharing it.
- **Open Access:** There is a distinct call for an increase on Open Access in the scientific community. Both in terms of work that would be shared via a DRN but also work that a DRN can access e.g., scientific articles and data.
- **Publishing:** One of the concerns of using ELNs has always been that there would be an unnecessary duplication of effort. Users are reluctant to spend a long-time curating notes and data when they have to then redo half the work to produce the final publication. There has long since been a call for a “generate report” or “generate thesis” button that would enable data and notes to be pulled together in at least a ‘semi-publication-ready’ state.
- **Sharing:** One of the key reasons for using a DRN would be to collaborate with others. Users want to be able to share work and data at different stages with their collaborators, and share in a range of ways be that singular files, whole notebooks, datasets etc.
- **Social Media:** Some users want to be able to share updates about their projects via social media. There should be an easy method to do this from a DRN.
- **Researcher Attribution:** There is a call to be able to better attribute data, code and components of work to different researchers when creating publications such that everyone who worked on a project gets properly acknowledged as opposed to just the main authors.
- **Repositories:** Users want a direct link between their DRN and a repository such that they can upload and download data/code/files seamlessly.

4.1.5 Collaboration & Management Features

The global pandemic necessitated an increase in the use of management-esque software. There are a number of features of collaboration and project/team management that would be required of a DRN.

- **Auditing:** One of the features that users have cited that they need to be able to replicate in any digital system is the audit trail that is vital both from a health and safety perspective but also when it comes to claiming patents. Which arguably should be easier to achieve using digital tools, but it needs to be done in a user-friendly way. There still needs to be moderation levels whereby managers can review, rate, approve and reject plans, COSHH forms, processes etc. These processes will work to protect IP rights.
- **Comments:** Users want the capacity to comment on all aspects of work (data, code, notes) to collaborate with their colleagues on every level.
- **Notifications:** Users want to be notified for a range of different activities, e.g. comments, messages, updates to work, updates to tasks etc.
- **Subscribe:** Users want to be able to subscribe to each other's work, e.g., notebooks, projects etc.
- **Team Management:** Team management is vital to any group project. There are lots of project management programs out there (Teams, Trello, Notion etc) and these should be incorporated into the overall DRN such that large scale projects can be managed, tasks can be allocated and work can be organised appropriately.

4.1.6 Domain Based Features

The physical science domain contains a wide range of different disciplines, which within themselves (e.g., chemistry) have a large amount of subdomains. This means that there are a great deal of domain specific formats, standards, databases, software packages etc. A DRN would need to be able to interface with all of these.

- **Chemical / Molecules:** Many of the researchers in the physical sciences community work with chemicals and molecules, and a system that has an inbuilt understanding of molecules and chemicals is one of the key types of domain software that users flock to. There should be standard lists of reagents and reaction schemes, and it should be possible to import reactions into a DRN. Additionally, many users have cited that a system that could automatically recognise chemicals in their notes would be incredibly useful.
- **Default Lists:** Another desirable feature that users have noted is the inclusion of default lists of relevant domain-based items, such as a standard list of instruments and reagents, default values for fields, a global database of chemical values etc. There should be a way to interface with standard taxonomies and vocabularies as well.
- **Equipment Interface:** Users have mentioned a desire for more modern equipment. Obviously PSDI can't control what equipment scientists have to hand, however this does mean that any DRN should be equipped to interface with modern equipment as well as legacy equipment. As noted above there should be standard lists of instruments, including mechanisms to interface with the different data types that these instruments produce.
- **Experiment Planning / Recording:** One of the main things that scientists use their paper-based lab notebooks for is to plan and record their experiments. Therefore, it is unsurprising that they would expect this functionality to be replicated in a DRN. Users want to be able to add all the usual information to their experiment (plan, title, date, conditions) and have requested more advanced features that would improve upon using a paper lab notebook. Users want to be able to copy and modify plans for future use, demonstrate the status of their experiments and mark them as completed when they are finished.

- **Health & Safety:** A DRN should enable users to link to and incorporate health and safety data into their work. There should be an index of all of the COSHH materials and users should be able to link to COSHH forms in their experiments. Experiment records should be automatically populated with risk assessment information based on the chemicals that are being used, and these should be automatically flagged upon entry. Users have also noted that additions such as a risk phrase vocabulary would be incredibly useful.
- **LIMS/ELN:** Just because ELNs aren't overly popular in academia, doesn't mean that they aren't being used in industry, or indeed that some academics aren't using them. A DRN should be able to interface with an ELN if necessary, particularly if a user is collaborating with someone else using one. Additionally, there needs to be links with LIMS software as this is much more widely used across the physical sciences community. This would require a level of collaboration with these software vendors to identify common data standards for interfacing.
- **Link to domain-based databases:** There are many databases out there that are well used by the physical sciences community, therefore any DRN would need to interface with these.
- **Link to domain-based software:** There is a wide range of domain-based software available (as demonstrated in Section 3.3.3). It would be entirely unrealistic to re-build all of these software packages within one DRN platform, therefore a DRN would need to interface with these such that scientists working across different domains could still use their required software alongside their notes and data.

4.1.7 Coding Support

As the amount of data generated by the physical sciences community continues to increase, there has been a vast surge in using computational methods to handle and analyse this data.

- **Coding:** Support for coding, and recording the process of developing code within or linked to a DRN is essential. Software such as Jupyter notebooks have become incredibly popular as data and code can be stored side by side and users can collaborate on coding projects, and any viable DRN would need to interlink with Jupyter notebooks and other software that offers similar functionality.
- **Versioning:** Hand in hand with coding comes the notion of version control. In order to record the process of developing code, different versions of the code at different points needs to be stored and there needs to be a capacity to roll back to different versions. Ideally a DRN would interface with GitHub and other popular version control services.

4.1.8 Metadata, Semantics & AI

As the use of computational techniques to handle data has increased, there has been a growing desire to capture and store metadata, and to use intelligent technologies to improve data handling.

- **AI Tools / Integration:** Users have requested integration with ML packages to handle and analyse data, and the capacity to store ML training data.
- **Metadata:** There is a high requirement for capturing and supporting metadata about documents, datasets and scientific content. Digital tools can automatically capture vast amounts of valuable metadata and the provenance trail, and where automatic capture is possible, they can prompt the user to add metadata as they go along, rather than forcing them into a burdensome process of metadata generation and curation at the end of the project when they are ready to move on.

- **Semantics:** There is a demand for the inclusion of semantics, for interoperability and to add context and meaning to the data captured in a DRN. Users want their data to be marked up/annotated semantically where appropriate with links to established ontologies and vocabularies. This will enable experiments, data, code etc to be classified, and will facilitate semantic search on concepts. This also enables projects and notebooks to be linked together, and for inferences to be made about similar work. Users have also requested inferences for the same molecules of reactions.

4.1.9 Searching

One of the key things that a computer can do immeasurably better than a human being is search efficiently through large quantities of data. Many of the features requested by users are related to search.

- **Domain Search:** Users also want to be able to do domain specific searches, such as searching by structure, reaction scheme, chemical etc.
- **Characteristics Search:** Users want to be able to search for datasets with specific characteristics.
- **Indexing:** Notebooks, data, notes, code all needs to be indexed such that it can be searched.
- **Keyword/Concept Search via Content Types:** Users want to be able to search through their data by keywords, and to search intelligently on concepts rather than just plain text (e.g., semantic search).
- **Literature Search:** Users want to be able to search through their work for inclusion of certain literature, access literature searches in bibliographic software, and search for similar types of literature.
- **Notebook Search:** Users want to be able to search through entire notebooks or collections of notebooks, including previous project notebooks.
- **Similarity Search:** Users want to be able to find similar content to their work, including similar data or experiments.
- **Visual Search:** Users want to be able to search by visual content such as images, they also want to be able to search for specific pieces of information in graphs.

4.1.10 Customisation & Extension

Notetaking is very personal, and yet within that personalisation lies different individuals' standard methods of doing work. Users need to be able to personalise their work but also create templates for their own methods.

- **Personalisable:** DRNs should provide a system where users can tailor them to their own specific research and domain. Linked to the notion of interfacing with domain-based software, users should be able to add plugins of their choice and they should be able to create their own plugins.
- **Templates:** Users want to be able to create their own templates for models, code, experiment plans, notes etc. They also want to capacity to share these templates and use those created by others.

4.1.11 Training & User Support

In addition to providing the features that users require, it is equally important to provide them with support to enable them to use a DRN in the most effective manner.

- **Training:** As with any new software system, training should be provided to users to demonstrate the different types of functionalities a DRN has to offer, and to show them the most effective ways of using one in their specific research.
- **User Documentation:** A DRN should come equipped with a decent level of user documentation to aid users in using the system.

4.2 Integration with Services

As discussed in the previous sections, the integration with software and services are key features that should be present in the DRN environment. Figure 15 shows an example range of services and facilities that could be of value to chemists in a Digital Research Notebook, taken from the fuller list of integrations identified in Section 4.1 that presents many different types of software and services that a DRN should integrate with. The services, software and hardware included are not exclusive. For example, for a particular department or organisation it may be useful to have a connection to internal human resources systems to provide information about personnel or organisational structures, and for many chemists having the capability to open analytical software directly through the ELN may be useful. For other disciplines, some of the same services shown here would be useful, but others that are discipline specific to that discipline could be added instead. Some of these facilities such as drawing tools, integration with instruments and LIMS and use of vocabularies could be built into the system, but a majority would be onerous and difficult or impractical to develop within a DRN tool itself, and therefore would only be feasible to implement by connecting to external service provider.

Figure 15: Service integration in a DRN (Chemist's Perspective)

This type of mass integration has yet to be tackled successfully, as demonstrated by the ELN landscape assessment in Appendix C. Although existing ELN systems have tried to facilitate this type of integration with other systems, this remains tricky to achieve and has typically meant creating very specific integrations with one or two types of software rather than creating a mechanism for a more universal integration.

One approach to providing such functionality within the DRN is to create plug-ins to a generic notebook to each service required, in that way a tailored DRN can be created by selecting a

connection to each service, software or hardware device desired. APIs and available standards for data formats are required to be able to create these custom plug-ins. The challenge would be the need to create a plug-in for every possible tool, instrument and service that may be needed even for a single discipline. As can be seen from the lack of integration options already available with existing ELNs, this is likely to be a challenging task, with ongoing problems with the use of proprietary formats for software and machines, and myriad services to choose from.

An approach to dealing with this problem is instead to create middleware software that can take the data from the DRN, different services, software and hardware and convert between them to reduce the effort involved in being able to connect to them, and also to make it easier to swap components in and out of the system as availability or desirability changes over time.

Figure 16: Example service integration through a middleware

The problem with this model is that the middleware layer must also have logic within to enable it to attach to every service. There may be dozens or more services for each service type. For example, there are many different chemical information services and databases available. The middleware needs to a customised application or component for each service to allow communication between the DRN and the service.

Figure 17: Example chemical information services requiring integration through middleware

5 Technologies & Software

To enable the overall connected research environment outlined within our DRN system there are a number of different technologies and software that could be used to aid the development and implementation. In this section we touch on some of the areas of technology and software that would be required in addition to the core notebooking software. This is not an exhaustive list of the technology/software areas that may be required, but shows some of the current technologies that could be employed to achieve more connected research recording.

5.1 Integration software

As discussed in Section 4.2, integration with other services and systems is a crucial element of the overall research system. In particular for the examples raised in Section 4.2 we may want to communicate with a chemical information service, bibliographic service or domain repository, among many other possibilities including more generic software such as data visualisation and analytics software, or software that enables coding such as Jupyter notebooks. Within this communication we want to send a request for information and receive a response back.

A majority of the domain-based software that our participants mentioned using (the full list of which can be found in Appendix D), is either Open-Source software, or custom-built software for a very specific purpose. Similarly, apart from the Microsoft Suite (which most University's and Companies provide access to) quite a lot of the more generic software e.g., for documentation, organisation etc is also Open-Source software. This means that there will be a requirement to interface with these different types of software, and potentially proprietary software as well where necessary, which will require common data standards to be in place. Where possible this can be done through the use of APIs, if the software offers this service.

Connection between systems and applications are most commonly facilitated through web APIs, with REST APIs (representational state transfer) being the most widely used architecture. Although other architectures such as SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) and RPC (Remote Procedural Call) are also implemented in different scenarios.

An alternative technology that could be implemented to facilitate the interaction with services is GraphQL^o which could act as an intermediary between the notebook and the different services. GraphQL specifies how information is exchanged between client and server and can be implemented in any programming language. At the most basic level a GraphQL application sends a query to a service asking for specific fields. What makes GraphQL different from REST API calls is that rather than having multiple end-points with fixed data structures, a GraphQL server exposes a single end-point with precisely the data that the client asked for. This means that a whole data request can be made in one go rather than having to send multiple separate requests to get all of the data required, without additional unnecessary data. This replaces multiple REST requests with a single call¹⁷, minimising data transmission and improving the efficiency of applications. A more detailed exploration of the application of GraphQL to this scenario is included in Appendix F.

5.2 Data format convertors

As demonstrated in Section 4.1, users wish to be able to integrate with a number of different services, and want to be able to import/export their data into different formats. The ELN Landscape assessment in Appendix C demonstrates the set of formats that are currently supported for import/export in ELNs, and whilst some of these are useful (e.g. MS Word, PDF, CSV), they are severely lacking in the diversity of file formats that are required by the physical sciences community, both in terms of more generic file formats such as JSON and HTML, and specific domain-based file formats.

There is a need for a data format converter to convert between different data types in order to facilitate data exchange between different services, and to allow users to collaborate using common formats. There are several options that could be used to achieve this. A new 'intermediary-format' could be created that can convert any file into its format, and vice versa. Alternatively, an existing more generic format (e.g. XML^p, JSON^q) could be used as that intermediary format. This could be achieved by building a specialist data converter that performs these operations. However, this would potentially only work for more generic formats, and domain based intermediary formats might need to be considered for specific disciplines to account for the diversity in types of data.

Alternatively, the DRN could interface with existing software programs that already facilitate conversions in certain areas, and additional code could be written to facilitate conversions for formats that are not represented. There are existing software programs that facilitate some conversions such as OpenBabel¹⁸, which converts between many of the different chemical formats with a specific focus on structural representation. There are some format converters for very specific domain formats such as WinSPEDAC^r, which is a software package that allows you to convert spectral data from one instrument manufacturer's format to another with some limitations. With respect to more generic data formats, there are a wide range of online format

^o <https://graphql.org/>

^p https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/XML/XML_introduction

^q <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

^r <http://www-naweb.iaea.org/napc/physics/PS/Softwares/Spedac.htm>

converters that exist. These would need to be compared and evaluated to see if particular ones were more viable for use than others.

In all approaches rigorous checks would need to take place to ensure that data is not lost between different format conversions.

5.3 Data Standards / Metadata

A frequently occurring topic in the discussion of requirements across much of the work undertaken in the PSDI case studies has touched on data standards in some fashion or other. Data standards are a critical element to facilitate interoperability, allowing exchange of data between different systems and researchers.

This includes:

- Standard file formats (in part facilitated through the implementation of data format converters – Section 5.2)
- Metadata standards
- Experimental protocol descriptions

A key element of the implementation of data standards comes in the adoption and utilisation of standards. It is all very well to have a defined format or specification, but if it isn't utilised by the stakeholders then it is effectively useless. In order to capitalise on the community adoption, standards should be utilised that are already widely adopted within the community, or defined by the governing bodies within a domain. Where these standards do not currently exist and there is a need for standard creation this should be developed in conjunction with the community and governing bodies to maximise adoption potential. Any new standards and methods for using/creating data standards should work within the remit of adhering to the FAIR data principles.

Another vital requirement that has been the source of much discussion, and was very clearly represented in the survey responses is the need for metadata and metadata standards. We need to capture metadata to describe our documents/data/code (e.g. author, date, file size) much of which can be done using Dublin Core^s and DCAT^t. We also need to capture domain based metadata about the context and content of our documents (e.g. experiment links, equipment links, chemicals represented). A detailed description of how this could be achieved is explored in Case Study 4.

Whilst it is widely agreed that the capturing of metadata is vital, the manual task of adding metadata to all documents, data, code etc is an arduous task, and therefore one that is frequently ignored. We need to consider methods of automatically capturing metadata for the user when they create their documents and data. There are a number of automatic tagging services that exist such as Refinitiv's Intelligent Tagging Service^u, and OntoText's Semantic Tagging Service^v. These do a decent job of providing tags which could be used as metadata for the more generic terms, but there is a lot of work to be done to provide automatic tagging in the different domain specific areas. Some projects have made a start in this area such as ChemicalTagger^w, but based on research undertaken by Kanza (2018)¹⁶ there is much work to

^s <https://www.dublincore.org/>

^t <https://dcat.org/>

^u <https://www.refinitiv.com/en/products/intelligent-tagging-text-analytics>

^v <https://www.ontotext.com/solutions/semantic-tagging/>

^w <http://chemicaltagger.ch.cam.ac.uk/>

be done in this area. Further, user research looking at these services suggested that whilst users would want a tool that did most of the work for them, they would also want to be able to edit it after the fact to make corrections. Therefore, a DRN would need to facilitate the automatic capturing of metadata in such a way that it could be customised and edited by different users.

5.4 Specialist Software

As highlighted by a previous research and responses to our survey (Section 3.3.3) there is a wide variety of specialist software being implemented in scientific research. Some of these may be specialist in function, but domain agnostic, some may be specific to a domain or subdomain and many of them are custom pieces of software produced by an individual or research group. Across these many pieces of software there is a huge variance in the openness of software, the level of documentation for the software, and the level of updates / support for the software.

Enabling a DRN to interface with this specialist software can largely be considered in two areas; facilitating access to the software / data from other programs and documenting the use of software / code to allow reproduction and validation of scientific research. The first of these areas has been discussed in other areas of the report as to how integration might be handled. It will not be possible to build integrations for every single piece of specialist software, however the provision of a framework will allow other integrations to be added where a need can be demonstrated by the community, or effort can be provided by invested parties.

The second area of reproduction and validation of scientific research is a complex area, and software is an important facet of reproducibility, particularly when so many stages of data analysis use computer programs and algorithms to process them. Changes and developments in software and computing means that even code and programs developed 10 years ago may not be usable today. Although 10 years may not be particularly long in the world of scientific data measurements it is a “very, very, very, very long time in the software world”¹⁹. There have also been many documented cases of errors in research arising due to software, such as; variation in code behaviour on different operating systems²⁰, errors in inherited in-house code²¹, and even formatting errors in spreadsheet software²².

Many of these errors encountered may be overcome by better testing and validation, which should be central to software development and implementation. However, it may often not even be clear in the research which software, version, or code excerpt has been used in the analysis. Where information has been included it still may not allow for reproduction of the analysis due to the omission of important information such as a specific run order, or even simple things like the operating system that the analysis was run on.

Overall the reproducibility of scientific analysis through software needs significant improvement. Areas that can be worked on include:

- Proper documentation of developed code
- Full description of the code implementation including software versions / code used e.g. AiiDA^x workflows
- Direct inclusion, where applicable, of the version of code used e.g. Jupyter notebooks or similar
- Better software citation for findability and recognition of software

^x <https://www.aiida.net/>

- Containerised environments which encapsulate the software for easy portability of applications e.g. Docker^y

This is not a newly discovered issue, but much work still remains to be done to improve interfaces with software and reproducibility of research. Expertise should also be leveraged from disciplines such as Research Software Engineering to enable better use of software in research.²³

5.5 Semantic Enrichment

The Semantic Web was conceptualized by Tim Berners-Lee as an extension to the WWW whereby “information is given well defined meaning, better enabling computers and people to work in cooperation”²⁴ In order to achieve this, several new standards and formats were created to facilitate interoperability, data sharing, and enable the construction of machine-readable metadata.

The primary data format for the Semantic Web is Resource Description Framework (RDF)²⁵ This format stores data in triples using a graph-based model of (subject --> predicate --> object) where the predicate denotes the relationship between the subject and the object. RDF facilitates storing data in a linked format, but typically it cannot sufficiently represent the necessary domain knowledge to provide context for the data. Ontologies were created to work with RDF to provide this additional knowledge. An ontology is essentially a vocabulary or dictionary for the Semantic Web²⁶. It provides a formal definition of the typical terms used within a domain, and details the hierarchy of classes that are used to represent the different levels of restrictions and relationships within a specific domain.

There are a number of ontologies that exist within the physical sciences. Some of the more popular ones are the three created by the Royal Society of Chemistry, RXNO - Named Reactions Ontology^z CMO - Chemical Methods Ontology^{aa} and MOP - Molecular Processes Ontology^{bb}, there is also the ChEBI - Chemical Entities of Biological Interest^{cc} ²⁷ and CHEMINF - terms commonly used in cheminformatics^{dd} ²⁸. Many others exist, Strömert et al produced a comprehensive review of ontologies in Chemistry ²⁹, and many others can be viewed on BioPortal^{ee} and other ontology repositories. In order to identify the usefulness and relevance of the different ontologies an evaluation would need to be performed, much like the one Kanza and Frey³⁰ undertook in the domain of Drug Discovery ontologies.

There are a number of different ways Semantic Web Technologies could be used to enrich a DRN. Users have expressed a desire for their documents and data to be marked up / annotated semantically with links to established ontologies and vocabularies. The ontologies will provide the standardised terms for such annotation. The Semantic Web has several annotation data formats for web-based documents. Resource Description Framework in Attributes (RDFa)³¹, Microdata³² and Java-Script Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD)³³. Each of these formats are HTML extensions that permit embedding rich metadata within HTML pages to provide additional information to the browser about the meaning of the pages and their context,

^y <https://www.docker.com/>

^z <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/rxno.html>

^{aa} <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/chmo.html>

^{bb} <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/mop.html>

^{cc} <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/chebi.html>

^{dd} <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/cheminf.html>

^{ee} <https://biportal.bioontology.org/>

meaning that Google is able to access this metadata to retrieve more accurate search results. Additionally, this could also be achieved by creating a knowledge graph about different documents and datasets in RDF. By creating these annotations and descriptions, this will enable the classification of the different data, documents, notebooks etc, and will facilitate semantic Search on concepts.

Semantic Search is another requirement by users, and is one of the key advantages of the Semantic Web. The main query language for the Semantic Web is SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL)³⁴, which enables data to be traversed and retrieved by using the graph structure of RDF, providing a much wider range of data paths than performing SQL queries on a standard relational database. The Shapes and Constraints Language (SHACL)³⁵ (the successor to the SPARQL Inferencing Notation - SPIN) is a relatively new addition to the Semantic Web Toolkit that was created as an RDF syntax to represent SPARQL complex constraints by specifying inferencing rules that can include mathematical expressions. By putting these rules in place, this will also enable projects and notebooks to be linked together and for inferences to be made about similar work.

Work will need to be undertaken to evaluate the suitable ontologies for use in Semantic enrichment, and identify gaps where new ontologies need to be created. The different methods for Semantic annotation will need to be experimented with to see which approaches work best, and whether any of the formats have particular advantages or not.

5.6 Hybrid technologies

The outcomes of this project have illustrated that there are many affordances of paper that still entice scientists to use it for several note-taking endeavours as opposed to using an electronic device. Rather than seek to entirely replace paper, it's worth considering how hybrid technologies can be incorporated into a DRN, as this could arguably provide the best of both worlds.

There is an increasing amount of hybrid notebook devices, that allow users to write on them in a manner akin to paper, whilst also digitally saving and preserving the notes, and in some cases automatically converting the handwritten notes into electronic text. Examples of these devices are the reMarkable^{ff}, and Boox^{gg}. There are also smart paper and pen systems such as the RocketBook^{hh}.

It would be interesting to explore different methods of increasing digitisation through unconventional methods such as taking photographs of lab pages and automatically saving them to note booking software such as Google Drive or OneNote. Simple software could be written to automatically organise lab notebook pages into dated folders, which would only require the users to take a photograph of each lab page using a phone app. This could then link to the users note booking software of choice such that whilst writing up their work they could easily access photographs of their lab books.

^{ff} <https://remarkable.com/>

^{gg} <https://www.boox.com/>

^{hh} <https://getrocketbook.co.uk/>

6 Recommendations & conclusions

Our research and findings for this case study support many of the original conclusions that have been outlined by our team over recent years. There is a clear requirement for better digital tools to enable scientists to conduct, share and publish their research, and yet there is still no one single system that supports this endeavour. This is namely because based on the diverse and extensive physical sciences community and the sheer level of different software requirements and tools out there, this is extremely unlikely to ever be possible. We need to move away from the idea that we can create one “one ELN to rule them all” and focus on how we can best use, improve and integrate the tools we have today.

Many of the results from our research and survey demonstrate that whilst scientists still remain unwilling to use ELNs and don't deem them to be useful, they still use a wide breadth of software tools to support their research. Digital Research Notebooks such as OneNote, Google Docs and Word are heavily utilized, as are Jupyter Notebooks, GitHub, and a wide range of domain specific software. There is a calling for these tools to play better together, and for common data standards to be adopted such that different software tools can be used in conjunction with each other. There is also an overwhelming call for improving metadata creation and usage. Further, this is a people issue as much as a hardware and software issue. Many of the issues that scientists encounter in their research also centre round user adoption and attitude.

There are two main areas that we need to consider:

- Improving digitisation
- Improving our digital records

Both of these need to be addressed (separately and in conjunction with one another) if we are to reach a point of a cohesive digital physical sciences community. We therefore propose that rather than try and reinvent the wheel again, we expend effort in training and educating our community, and applying user centered design methodologies to develop methods to enhance existing DRNs and work to facilitate links between existing domain-based software, and improve metadata design and capture. In other words, we need to create a fully-fledged infrastructure that can support this. In terms of PSDI this means:

PSDI core should facilitate:

- Links between DRNs (e.g. OneNote) and Domain Based Software
- Common data standards that can be used across DRNs and Domain Based Software
- Common metadata standards that can be used across DRNs and Domain Based Software
- Ontologies/Taxonomies to describe scientific data
- Data format conversion
- Access to high quality open scientific literature
- Adequate description of chemical structure
- DOI generation / linking
- API's to access different types of data
- Data exchange
- Licensing data and scientific research
- Citations and attributions for all types of data (datasets, documents, code)

A digital research notebook on or integrating with PSDI should:

- Interface with existing notebooking software
- Interface with organisational software and team management tools
- Interface with domain-based software
- Interface with equipment and lab systems
- Support multiple content types and work with multiple standard scientific data formats
- Offer multiple interaction methods (e.g. handwriting, typing, voice) and input tools (hybrid devices, mobile devices etc)
- Include generic and domain-based metadata
- Include semantic technologies where appropriate
- Secure data access and storage
- Support data management
- Export / import data in different formats
- Track data provenance
- Provide audit trails
- Support coding and version control
- Be fully indexable and searchable

6.1 Key Recommendations

Process Recording: This should be embedded in all parts of PSDI.

PSDI Core: PSDI will need a core element, which will provide the relevant services and functionalities such as those listed above. Then there will be additional technologies surrounding the core that will interface with these core services.

Technology Integration: Software and services within the system need to be interoperable to allow them to be tailored to the different environments of the individual researchers. To facilitate this usage, the full extent of the current technology landscape needs to be understood and links need to be established between existing technologies.

Develop Prototype: Develop a prototype plugin to demonstrate an interface between a generic DRN and an established, documented service to show proof of concept. (Short Term)

Metadata & Standards: To underpin these recommendations in CS6, models are required for the metadata and standards used in domain data. Where these don't exist currently, resource should be invested in developing them.

Future ways of working: The proposed or developed systems need to factor in changes to working practices, advances in technology and the evolving nature of scientific research.

DMPs: PSDI should enable researchers to develop or interact with Data Management Plans and support them in enacting them.

User Experience & Adoption: This is a sociotechnical task, and as such as need to consider people in the design of the system and social aspects in the rollout/implementation of any system. More training and education needs to be provided in the areas of research data management, and handling data at all stages of the research data lifecycle.

6.2 Next steps

In order to achieve these recommendations, we propose the following research activities.

6.2.1 Technology Studies & Prototypes

- Software Study & DRN Prototype (NB: Must run across academic and industry)
 - **Software Elicitation:** Use results from PSDI survey and Kanza (2019) to create a categorized list of different software in the physical sciences, which we can use to survey the wider community to understand which ones are most widely used.
 - **Software Analysis:** Analyse the software for the following aspects:
 - Open Source
 - How much it Costs
 - Data Formats (import and export)
 - Platform / Web based
 - API
 - Access / Authentication methods
 - **Service Identification:** Use results to identify most popular DRN, and priority services for integration into DRN that provide the most benefit for the community and pilot an integration, for example one of the following integrations:
 - Bibliographic services
 - Scientific data repositories & databases
 - Chemical information databases
 - Service providers
 - Publishers
 - DOI generation / linking

It would make sense to do this for services that some work has already been done before and where there are already pre-existing relations, for example, ChemSpider as a Chemical Information Database, National Crystallography Service as a service provider, and ChemSpider SyntheticPages as a publisher. (The UI designs are partially based on these scenarios already). This can also be used to identify any gaps or services that need to be created.

- **Prototype Investigation:** Different ways of connecting the DRN to other services could be investigated, for example:
 - A plug-in to directly talk to a service
 - An intermediate service (for example based on GraphQL) that could later be expanded to aggregate data from multiple service providers).
- **Prototype Creation:** Based on the results above, create a prototype plugin to demonstrate an interface between the most popular DRN and a priority service

6.2.2 Standards

- Metadata Study
 - A thorough investigation of the metadata provided and required by various services that would be desired for a Digital Research Notebook to interact with, and what benefits and capabilities these different services can provide for users.
 - Work should be done to identify metadata schemas for the DRN that would enable the right data and metadata to be displayed/captured for the user in the DRN user interface and that would be needed to integrate meaningfully with the

existing services out there, and any services being developed by the PSDI. These schemas should be documented as part of the design process.

- Research existing projects looking at interoperability and metadata
- Semantic Web / Ontology Study
 - Investigate relevant ontologies and semantic systems for use with DRNs and Domain based software
 - Investigate relevant taxonomies that could be converted into ontologies for use with DRNs and Domain based software
- Support for communities / domain to create metadata / ontologies.

6.2.3 Process recording behaviour and support for Computer-based research

- Investigate process recording behaviour for researchers working in computational disciplines or with existing data, for example using workflows, Jupyter notebooks, own code, analytical software, and High-Performance Computing. There is a high likelihood that processes are not being adequately recorded in this space which may lead to problems with reproducibility and validation in the long term.
- Investigate how systems for the management and storage of code and workflows could be updated to facilitate better process recording (rather than the current scraps of paper model) and whether there would be any benefit, and feasibility for, integration with a generic electronic notebook.
- Consider furthering previous investigations and implementations for documenting and visualising workflows for preservation and reuse as described in Willoughby & Frey 2017³⁶. The initial research was carried out in the KNIME workflow tool described in Appendix A, but requests have been made to investigate implementation of such a facility in other workflow tools.
- Examine what relevant computational services are available for researchers in the physical sciences and whether connection to such services would be of value within a DRN.

6.2.4 Enabling the future lab / ways of working

- Hybrid Study:
 - Investigate the range of hybrid notebook tools available to see how well they work overall
 - Investigate how/if hybrid notebook tools can be linked with a DRN
 - Investigate how/if hybrid notebook tools can be linked with Domain based software
- Smart Lab
 - Investigate how a DRN could be linked into a Smart Lab
 - Investigate the use of Voice in this scenario
- Investigate how to accommodate future ways of working (remote, hybrid, in person) using the range of hardware tools we have available (mobiles, tablets, e-ink devices, laptops, desktops)

6.2.5 Planning, data management, team management, and collaboration

Digital Research Notebooks provide an opportunity for capturing important elements of the scientific record in one place and acting as a place for planning, sharing and discussion. This process begins with the Data Management Plan and ends with the results of the research ready to be shared and published. Our focus has been on the individual researchers, but it is clear that

we can use or implement tools for facilitating team management and cross team collaborations. Further research to understand these elements would be of value.

- Study of Data Management Plan (DMP) use, sharing, storage and maintenance within research organisations
- Study of researcher behaviour, task management, and data/status sharing within teams and cross team collaborators
- Investigate how metadata and content from DMPs could be utilised and interacted with within a DRN
- Investigate what features of a DRN (or connectivity to existing systems) could support research within and between teams. E.g., it may be helpful to be able to connect a human resources software system to a DRN for the purpose of authorisation or to be able to display/populate departmental or contact information for a particular notebook author.

6.2.6 User Experience & Adoption

- Creating interactive prototypes based on integration with tools where we have already done work
- Creating interactive prototypes for different communities
- Investigate methods for improving user adoption
- Raise awareness and upskill people to be able to do research data management properly and use PSDI as a mechanism to enable this. This would include developing training in several aspects of software and RDM processes.

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Appendix

A. KNIME for Process Recording

Scientific Workflow Management Systems for process recording in Data Science.

With the importance of reproducibility of scientific processes and data when publishing, a new emphasis is being put on process recording around the scientific community. While electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs) provide this for the bench chemist, scientific workflow management systems (WMSs) could be a way for the computational chemist to record their processes as they work. This user story will reflect on the uses of scientific workflows (namely the KoNstanz Information Miner – KNIME) and their applicability to process recording.ⁱ

Workflow management systems in general provide a way to order processes and run them consecutively while being able to alter settings and parameters within the individual processes and the workflow as a whole. Moreover, the scientific packages built into these systems allow for chemical processes to be captured and *in silico* experiments to be run. Liew et al. (2016)ⁱⁱ highlight 7 different WMSs and note their applications across various scientific domains eg. Taverna for the life-sciences and KNIME for cheminformatics.

While WMSs provide inherent reproducibility of data as a workflow given the same input will always produce the same output (if no parameters are changed), the processes themselves may not be as obviously reproducible. WMSs that provide graphical representation of the processes (for example, KNIME) are a step in the right direction in terms of a reproducible workflow as at a glance the nodes of the graph can be recaptured and the connections between them redrawn. However, in terms of publishing the parameters of each of these nodes aside from publishing the whole workflow, together with their file dependencies and node configurations (as seen on sites such as myExperiment.org) there are few other options.ⁱⁱⁱ For KNIME specifically, the KNIME hub provides this platform as users can publish entire workflows as well as individual nodes they have created for the community to use.^{iv}

KNIME for recording experimental processes.

KNIME is a free to use workflow management system with scientific extensions available due to collaborations with the CDK and RDKit as well as external pharmaceutical companies with uses for the KNIME software. The workflows themselves comprise of 'nodes' which are packaged pieces of code each with their own function. These nodes are connected together and data flows from one node to another once the initial operation has been completed on all the data points in the input. Each individual node has a traffic light-based system denoting if the node is unconfigured (red), configured but not yet run (amber) or fully configured and run to completion (green). This makes protocols easy to debug as you know exactly which node in the workflow has not finished running or caused an error. Furthermore, workflows do not have to be run to completion as individual nodes can be run and the data viewed after each step using the 'Execute and Open Views' function. This not only aids debugging but also empowers data scientists to monitor their data throughout their workflow. The visual nature of the programming allows for process documentation while creating the workflow and the addition of notes around the workflow increases the clarity of the documentation and the workflow's reproducibility.

Other advantages of KNIME include its ease of use with an intuitive GUI and free introductory workshops available to aid people new to the software. The KNIME hub and node repository which both can be viewed within the application also help KNIME users to know the full functionality available in KNIME.^{iv} The KNIME hub in particular is an active community allowing for greater collaboration as whole workflows can be uploaded to be used by others. It also acts as a repository for trusted developers to detail nodes and extensions that they have created. As nodes are already pre-packaged pieces of code which perform their own operation, no classical coding experience is needed to make them work. This does not mean that coding skills are not usable within KNIME as there are existing nodes that allow for R and python code to be run on the data. Also, KNIME workflows can be incorporated into python processes with the use of `knime(py)`, a python library that takes data from python and runs a KNIME workflow on it.^v The library also fully supports the use of pandas data frames as input tables for KNIME workflows and could be used to streamline data cleaning and pre-processing steps to aid data analysis.

Barriers to using KNIME.

The simplicity of coding processes using the nodes in KNIME does come with its disadvantages, the main trade-off for this is flexibility. When coding within KNIME you are limited to the functionality already available in the node repository. N.B. KNIME does allow users to develop and publish their own nodes, however some knowledge of Java is needed to do this. There also comes with this a certain entry-level barrier in that new users may not know what functionality exists within scientific workflows. Alongside this, scientists may be hesitant to switch their current processes to workflows as years of coding experience make it easier to use their code rather than learning how to build a workflow.

In summary, WMSs such as KNIME are useful in process recording due to their graphical nature. Also, although scientists may be cautious to use workflows as opposed to hard coded methods because of the limited flexibility available within the nodes, their reliability lends themselves to automating repetitive tasks such as data pre-processing (as highlighted by Liew et al. (2016)).ⁱⁱ This together with being implemented alongside python (running python script in KNIME and running workflows in python using `knime(py)`) could act as a simple way for scientists to show their processes in detail, enhancing the reproducibility of their work.

ⁱ Berthold, M. R.; Cebon, N.; Dill, F.; Gabriel, T. R.; Kötter, T.; Meinel, T.; Ohl, P.; Thiel, K.; Wiswedel, B. KNIME - the Konstanz Information Miner: Version 2.0 and Beyond. *SIGKDD Explor. Newsl.* **2009**, *11* (1), 26–31. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1656274.1656280>.

ⁱⁱ Liew, C. S.; Atkinson, M. P.; Galea, M.; Ang, T. F.; Martin, P.; Hemert, J. I. V. Scientific Workflows: Moving Across Paradigms. *ACM Comput. Surv.* **2016**, *49*(4), 66:1-66:39. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3012429>.

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.myexperiment.org/home>

^{iv} <https://hub.knime.com>

^v <https://github.com/knime/knimepy>

B. Process Recording Survey

This survey was designed in conjunction with collaborators from case study 8. This survey was designed to collect data about current working practices in the physical sciences domain, looking at how scientists are recording and sharing their data, what software they use, what structures they work with, what features they require and how things have changed since the COVID-19 pandemic.

Ethics approval was obtained from the University of Southampton Ethics and Research Governance Team through application ERGO/FEPS/70431 and our participants were provided with our participant information sheet and data protection plan prior to their participation in the survey.

Survey Questions

Below is a list of survey questions as presented to our participants

Consent

1. I have read and understood the participant information sheet linked above and have had the opportunity to ask questions about the survey. I agree to take part in this survey and agree for my data to be used for the purpose of this study. I understand that my participation is voluntary and I may withdraw (at any time) for any reason without my participation rights being affected.

Yes

Recording & Storing your data

2. For each of the following types of work, how do you currently record it?

Matrix

	On Paper	Electronically	A mix of both	N/A
Doing an experiment in the lab				
Doing an experiment outside of the lab				
Looking at literature				
Thinking about / planning your work				
Performing calculations to support your research				
Analysing your data				
Writing up your work				

3. How is your work organised / linked together **within a project**?
Free text
4. How is your work organised / linked together **between projects**?
Free text

Structural Representation

5. What does the term 'structure' mean to you in your research?
Free text
6. When is it important to use digital representations of structure in your research?
Free text

7. Which of the following structure representations do you use when communicating or undertaking your research?

Multiple Selection

- Formula / Composition
- Compound Name
- Structure Diagram
- Computational Chemistry Formats
- Crystallographic formats (e.g. CIF)
- Chemistry Formats (e.g. MOL file, SMILES)
- Identifiers (e.g. InChI, CAS registry numbers)
- None of the above
- Other

Software & Collaboration

8. Do you make use of any digital research notebooks? If so, which ones?
E.g. OneNote, Jupyter Notebooks, MBook, LabArchive, SciNote, RSpace

Free text

9. Do you use software specifically for collaborating with colleagues / sharing research? If so, which software?

Free text

10. What other software do you use in your research?

Please list software names and include web-based or specialist / domain-based software if used.

Free text

Sharing your data

11. Are you making your data available to others, if so how? (e.g. Via a repository or GitHub)

Free text

12. Does it conform to FAIR standards?

(Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)

Radio button

- Yes
- Partially
- No
- I'm not familiar with FAIR
- N/A I don't share data

13. Are there any restrictions that you have encountered either whilst sharing or accessing data?

Free text

Enabling your future research

14. Since the COVID-19 pandemic have you changed your research methods with respect to recording and sharing your work? If so, what aspects are digital that didn't used to be?

Free text

15. Are any aspects now no longer digital that used to be?

Free text

16. Do you think these changes will be permanent?

Free text

17. Are there limitations or barriers in your current systems that prevent your research from reaching its full potential, if so what?

Free text

18. Assuming a fully digital world, please select up to five features that would be important to your work

Matrix

	1 st – Most important	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	Lower than 5 th / not important
Access to reference quality data						
Easily combining data from multiple sources						
Publishing data						
Repositories						
Availability of standards e.g. metadata, file formats, ontologies etc						
Platform for recording and managing data / information.						
Access to compute infrastructure / platforms for running code						
Exploiting AI / Machine Learning methods						
Bringing together experimental and simulation data						

19. If technology could do one thing to make your work easier, what would it be?

Free text

About you and your research

20. What research area(s) do you work in?

Free text

21. Please provide a description of the type of data that you work with

Free text

22. With respect to your research, which of these roles do you undertake? (Please select all that apply)

Multiple selection

- Creating Data Management Plans
- Generating new data
- Obtaining existing data
- Analysing data
- Managing data
- Curating data
- Sharing & Publishing data
- Other

23. Is there anything else relevant that you would like to tell us about this subject?

Free text

24. Would you be willing to be contacted to take part in a Focus Group as a follow up to this questionnaire? If so please put your name and email address in the box below.

Free text

25. Where are you based?

Radio button

- In the UK
- Outside the UK

Survey Results

The survey was circulated on a variety of social media platforms and mailing lists within the physical sciences research community. The survey was open for a period of 5 weeks and received 44 responses.

The discussion on the analysis of the results can be found in Section 3. Raw anonymised results from the survey will be published on the PSDI website.

C. ELN Landscape Assessment

There are dozens of Electronic Laboratory Notebooks currently available, many of which are highly tailored to particular disciplinary specialisations as shown in Figure C. 1. There are also a number of generic notebook tools or even word processors available that can be used to capture the day-to-day scientific process.

Figure C. 1: Discipline specialisations within current ELNs

ELNs can be used for storage beyond the day-to-day notes and the majority allow the attachment or import of different file types. For example, files could contain safety information for the experiment, publications or methods that have been used as part of the experiment design, or images and data produced during and after the experiment. As shown in Figure C. 2, for those ELNs with public documentation available, the most widely supported file formats for including in the ELN are Microsoft Excel and Word, and often the ELN is able to process these files to convert them to the ELN format or enable the user to edit the content within the ELN. Many ELNs allow users to upload any file type to the ELN for storage, but the software does not attempt to process the files and there is limited functionality to view and modify them within the ELN. A large number also specifically mention that images can be attached or imported to the notes in the ELN. More rarely, common data formats such as CSV, TSV, and XML can be imported and in a small number of ELNs some discipline specific data formats such as chemical drawings, spectra, DNA sequences, biological structures, protocols and specific instrument data.

IMPORT FORMATS

Figure C. 2: Support for different file types within ELNs

There are a variety of reasons why a researcher might want to be able to export content from the ELN. Although many ELNs enable others who are authorised to view the content, and in fact some ELNs enable their authors to use them as Open Notebooks, where they are fully open and visible by anyone with a link to the notebook, authors may wish to share their notebooks or individual experiment records in a different format. For example, a user might want to share their record with a collaborator or an auditor, or they might want to package the record and data for supplementary materials. For many researchers there are regulations that require that the records and the data be stored for the long term so content may need to be exported so that it can be backed-up or preserved. The ELN market is quite volatile and ELN vendors regularly appear and disappear over time, and so the ability to be able to get content out of the ELN so it can still be accessed in some form is highly desirable.

EXPORT FORMATS

Figure C. 3: Options for exporting data from ELNs

Figure C. 3 shows the options available for exporting files from those ELNs where public documentation is available. PDF can be seen to be the most common format. PDF is a handy format for user readable content, and relatively easy to program on many platforms, but as mentioned previously it is a format that is not very machine friendly, and it can be very difficult to extract content that makes any semantic sense programmatically. Export as html and Microsoft Word are also fairly common, but they suffer from the same kinds of problems. XML and JSON are machine readable options and in a small number of ELNs, discipline specific data formats are exportable such as HL7 for healthcare, DNA sequences, ChemSketch, and some protocols and metadata formats.

INTEGRATION CAPABILITIES

Figure C. 4: Documented integration capabilities of ELNs

Import and export options of the majority of ELNs are not machine-readable formats as discussed, but some ELNs provide additional functionality for interoperability between the ELNs and other systems built in. Figure C. 4 shows the integration capabilities of those ELNs that provide public documentation. The most common integration is with Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) to provide access to inventory, supplies and sample tracking information. In a couple of cases, the ELN is actually an extension of the LIMS system itself. Another common integration is with Bibliographic systems, such as Mendeley and PubMed to enable the import of citations and documentation into the notebook. Several of the ELNs provide integration with specific databases, repositories, or cloud storage for the purpose of long-term preservation, although it is unclear how many of these enable export in a machine-readable format. A relatively small percentage of ELNs provide integration with Web Services, and even fewer have their own API. These features may enable developers to access information in the notebooks and potentially develop their own plug-ins to extend the system. Only a single ELN mentions integration with legacy ELNs, highlighting the lack of support for migration even within the same vendor, let alone to between different ELNs. It is perhaps little surprising few vendors mention integration with instruments given that the vast majority of instruments are now producing data in digital form. This may be due to a lack of common standards for data from digital instruments, with each instrument requiring a unique parser to be written for the data to be understood by the ELN. Unsurprisingly, the vast majority of ELNs with integration capabilities and anything more than very basic import and export facilities are those that charge commercial prices for the software or licenses.

Despite the fact that ELNs should be able to effectively create and collect metadata to describe the data and other resources captured within, very few even mention metadata. Those that do mention them tend also to be those that integrate with specific instruments, software or systems and format data to match the common representations for these. A small number mention the use of standard vocabularies and a couple mention metadata capture from keywords and extraction of DOIs and citations from publications. The LabTrove ELN developed by Southampton University remains one of the most functional ELNs from the point of view of metadata capture and capabilities.

D. Software Categories

In Question 10 of the survey, the participants were asked what other software they used. We took these results and split them up into individual pieces of software, and removed all duplicates. From this we had a list of 209 pieces of software. We categorised these using the categories from our previous software research and identified new categories from the remaining items. Table D. 1 shows a full alphabetised list of the categories and the pieces of software within these categories.

Table D. 1: Full categorised list of software from PSDI Survey Question 10

Category	Software
CAD Software	Autodesk inventor
CAD Software	onshape.com
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	Chemistry Open Database
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	CSD (Cambridge Structural Database)
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	dragon
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	icsd
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	mordred
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	NIST
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	nomad
Chemical Database & Informatics Software	openbabel
Chemistry Bibliographic Databases	JabRef
Chemistry Bibliographic Databases	Mendeley
Chemistry Bibliographic Databases	SciFinder
Chemistry Bibliographic Databases	Zenodo
Chemistry Bibliographic Databases	Zotero
Coding software	Anaconda
Coding Software	debuggers
Coding Software	docker engine/swarm
Coding Software	expo
Coding software	Fortran
Coding Software	Git
Coding Software	jax
Coding Software	kubernetes
Coding Software	MATLAB
Coding Software	p4merge
Coding Software	pandoc Vue.js for building GUIs FastAPI/pydantic
Coding Software	pymol
Coding Software	Python
Coding Software	NumPy
Coding Software	SciPy
Coding Software	PyTorch
Coding Software	R
Coding Software	R-chis
Coding Software	RDkit

Coding Software	ruby and crystal programming languages
Coding Software	Spyder
Coding Software	Visual Studio Code
Communication Software	Gmail
Communication Software	Signal
Communication Software	Slack
Communication Software	Zoom
Crystallographic Software	apex4
Crystallographic Software	ConQuest
Crystallographic Software	Crystal17
Crystallographic Software	Crystaldiffract
Crystallographic Software	Crystalexplorer
Crystallographic Software	CrystalisPro
Crystallographic Software	CrystalMaker
Crystallographic Software	CrystalOptimizer
Crystallographic Software	CrystalPredictor
Crystallographic Software	dash
Crystallographic Software	DMACRYS
Crystallographic Software	encifer
Crystallographic Software	gsas
Crystallographic Software	IsoDistort (web based, https://stokes.byu.edu/iso/isodistort.php)
Crystallographic Software	Jana2006
Crystallographic Software	Match
Crystallographic Software	Olex2
Crystallographic Software	platon
Crystallographic Software	Gsas-II
Crystallographic Software	Powder diffraction analysis (GSAS, GSASII, FullProf)
Crystallographic Software	PowDLL
Crystallographic Software	profex
Crystallographic Software	Shelx suite
Crystallographic Software	Topas
Crystallographic Software	webcsd
Crystallographic Software	wingx
Data Visualisation & Analysis	ACD analytical software
Data Visualisation & Analysis	CellProfiler
Data Visualisation & Analysis	CYLView
Data Visualisation & Analysis	DataWarrior
Data Visualisation & Analysis	gnuplot
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Grace
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Gwyddion
Data Visualisation & Analysis	JMP
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Mantid
Data Visualisation & Analysis	MiniTab
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Origin

Data Visualisation & Analysis	POV-ray
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Spotfire Analyst
Data Visualisation & Analysis	super flip
Data Visualisation & Analysis	VESTA
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Veusz
Data Visualisation & Analysis	Virscidian LC-MS (and more) software
Data Visualisation & Analysis	WebPlot Digitizer
Data Visualisation & Analysis	xmgrace
Database Software	ArangoDB
Database Software	Apache Jena Fuseki
Database Software	MongoDB
Database Software	MySQL
Database Software	SQL
General document processing	Flare
General document processing	emacs
General document processing	Google Docs
General document processing	jEdit
General document processing	LaTeX
General document processing	Libreoffice
General document processing	Lyx
General document processing	MS Excel
General document processing	MS 365 Suite
General document processing	MS PowerPoint
General document processing	MS Word
General document processing	OneNote (and on ipad)
General document processing	Overleaf
General document processing	PDF Xchange editor
General document processing	tex/latex
General document processing	LaTeXIt
General document processing	TeXStudio
General document processing	TexShop
Image processing Software	Adobesuite
Image processing Software	AIPS (Astronomical Image Processing System)
Image processing Software	CORELDraw
Image processing Software	FIJI
Image processing Software	GIMP
Image processing Software	ImageJ
Image processing Software	Inkscape
Image processing Software	paint.NET
Image processing Software	PaintShopPro
Instrument Control	ChemStation
Instrument Control	LabVIEW
Instrument Control	Mettler-Toledo iC software suite
Instrument Control	trios

Instrument Control	Unchained Labs Automation Studio and associated viewers
Machine Learning	scikit-learn
Machine Learning	Tensorflow
Molecular Editor Software	ChemDraw
Molecular Editor Software	marvin
Molecular Editor Software	Mercury
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Atomic Simulation environment
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Autodock vina
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	BioSimSpace
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Charmm-Gui
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	ChimeraX
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	DL_Poly
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Geant4
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	gromacs
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	GULP
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Gypsum-DL
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Lammps (classical MD)
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Materials Studio
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	MDAnalysis
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	molden
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	nwchem
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	OpenEye
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	OpenMM
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	Ovito (visualisation)
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	SnapGene
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	tinker
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	VASP
Molecular Modelling & Simulation Software	VMD
Nanostructures Modelling Software	Aztec
Nanostructures Modelling Software	Quantum Espresso
Organisational Software	DropBox
Organisational software	Google drive
Organisational software	iCloud
Organisational Software	Mural
Organisational Software	Project management
Organisational Software	slurm
Organisational Software	Trello
Other	Adobe Acrobat
Other	Agilent
Other	CASA (Common Astronomy Software Applications)
Other	EIMS online mode solver
Other	Cytoscape
Other	In-house/custom software
Other	KLayout

Other	MadGraph
Other	RNAppbees
Other	TeamViewer
Other	UnityMol
Other	Wolfram Alpha
Other	Wolfram Mathematica
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	AlmaBTE
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Amber
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	BoltzTraP(2)
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	CASTEP
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	chemshell
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Delphes
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Density functional theory (DFT) codes
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	ELK
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	FHI-aims
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	gamess
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Gaussian
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	hybrid qm/mm
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Lumerical
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Molpro
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	multiwfn
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Orca
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	siesta
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	Quantum mechanics software
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	ShengBTE
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	wxmacmolpld
Quantum Chemistry and Solid State Physics Software	xtb
Simulation (non-chemical)	Cluspro
Simulation (non-chemical)	COMSOL
Simulation (non-chemical)	COPASI
Simulation (non-chemical)	Pythia
Simulation (non-chemical)	RNA fold
Spectroscopic Software	CasaXPS
Spectroscopic Software	diffract.eva
Spectroscopic Software	iNMR
Spectroscopic Software	MassHunter
Spectroscopic Software	MestreNova NMR
Spectroscopic Software	mMass
Spectroscopic Software	Regress Pro
Spectroscopic Software	spectragryph
Spectroscopic Software	topspin
Spectroscopic Software	turbo mass
Workflow software	knime

E. DRN Features

In order to ascertain what features users would want from a DRN, we collated together desired features from three different sources:

- **Survey Results:** We asked users several questions that could elicit desired features, including how technology could make their life easier, what features they would perceive to be the most important for a DRN, and the limitations and barriers they currently face.
- **User Stories:** As demonstrated in Section 2, part of the research for this case study was to produce a large number of storyboards and flows based on user roles and requirements. The features detailed in these were also extracted for the purpose of this exercise.
- **Mural Boards:** During the PSDI partner meetings, several Mural Boards were set up for collaborative use during the meetings for partners and team members to brainstorm about potential functionality and features. These features were also extracted from these different Mural Boards.

The full list of features have been categorised twice, into high level categories and sub categories. Table E. 1 shows the full breakdown of these features and their categories:

Table E. 1: Categorised list of features obtained from engagement activities

High Level Category	Feature Category	Feature
Coding Support	Coding	Code testing
Coding Support	Coding	Code to deal with data
Coding Support	Coding	Collaborative coding
Coding Support	Coding	Document Code
Coding Support	Coding	Record process of developing Code
Coding Support	Coding	Record process of developing model/simulation
Coding Support	Coding	Translation of interactive command-line testing of parameters into a script (including understanding 'delete last thing, it didn't work'), and script documentation generation suitable for users (topic-based, indexed) not just for developers.
Coding Support	Versioning	Establish version of DRN
Coding Support	Versioning	Version control
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Audit Trails
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Lock plans and risk assessments
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Mark as audited
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Moderation: review / approve / reject / rate all data/Code/plans/etc
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Protect Intellectual Property rights
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Reconfigure notebook to share when experiment is marked as complete/approved

Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Review and rate experiment
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Review process / data for validity
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	See activity logs
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	See when notebook was last audited
Collaboration & Management Features	Auditing	Sign off entries
Collaboration & Management Features	Comments	Configurable comment capabilities
Collaboration & Management Features	Notifications	Configurable notifications for all changes
Collaboration & Management Features	Subscribe	Have sign up button for notebook
Collaboration & Management Features	Subscribe	Register interest in projects
Collaboration & Management Features	Subscribe	Subscribe to other researchers/notebooks/projects
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Bulletin board / forum style space
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Create a homepage for notebook
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Message board
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Page statistics
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Plan allocation of capacity
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Recent activity feed
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	See overview of research
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Share an update on a notebook
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Task Management
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Team communication
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Team homepage for information in the same place
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Team leaders control data of group
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Team notebooks
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	Track meetings and progress
Collaboration & Management Features	Team Management	View collaborators files

Customisation Extension	&	Personalisable	Add own plugins
Customisation Extension	&	Personalisable	Create user profiles
Customisation Extension	&	Personalisable	Personalisable
Customisation Extension	&	Personalisable	Tailor system to research domain / researcher
Data Features		API Access	API access to data
Data Features		Data Access	Authentication covers login, data permissions etc.
Data Features		Data Access	Data Access controls with different levels
Data Features		Data Access	See who is accessing data
Data Features		Data Conversion	Conversion tool
Data Features		Data Conversion	Data format converter
Data Features		Data Conversion	Data ingest processes
Data Features		Data Exchange	Data exchange platform
Data Features		Data Integration	Collate together experimental and simulation data
Data Features		Data Integration	Combine data across a team
Data Features		Data Integration	Combine data from multiple sources
Data Features		Data Integration	Easily combining data from multiple sources
Data Features		Data Management	Central database for output data
Data Features		Data Management	Create data management plan
Data Features		Data Management	Curation of existing data resources
Data Features		Data Management	Define data processing pipeline
Data Features		Data Management	Platform for recording and managing data
Data Features		Data Quality	Assurance on quality of data
Data Features		Data Quality	Criteria to categorise resource as trusted
Data Features		Data Quality	Quality check data
Data Features		Data Retention	Perserve data indefinitely
Data Features		Data Retention	Remove obsolete data offline / soft delete
Data Features		Data Retention	Store data for a specified period of time
Data Features		Data Security	Data Security
Data Features		Data Security	Secure storage, backup and archives
Data Features		Data Standards	Data provided in clear and accessible formats
Data Features		Data Standards	Enforce consistent standards.
Data Features		Data Standards	Ensure integrity of data and metadata
Data Features		Data Standards	Have a universal control and data output language
Data Features		Data Standards	Shim layers as a common interface
Data Features		Data Standards	Standardised file formats that work and everyone adheres to.
Data Features		Data Standards	Standardised methods of referring to chemicals
Data Features		Data Standards	Use domain standards

Data Features	Data Storage	Archive at the time of creation	
Data Features	Data Storage	Archive Notebook	
Data Features	Data Storage	Automatic saves	
Data Features	Data Storage	Backup/archive	
Data Features	Data Storage	Can handle large datasets	
Data Features	Data Storage	Permanent storage options for data. Current limitation of storage providers, i.e. Google, Amazon, Dropbox, etc. is the issue that if you close or lose the account, access to previous uploads is also revoked -- can't refer to them for access to data in articles.	
Data Features	Data Storage	Secure storage, backup and archives	
Data Features	Data Support	Deal with all different stages of data (raw, cleaned, processed, analysed)	
Data Features	Data Support	Download and utilise catalog data	
Data Features	Data Support	Drag data from other resources into DRN	
Data Features	Data Support	Include data from other software	
Data Features	FAIR	Data curation for FAIR	
Data Features	FAIR	Publishing FAIR data	
Data Features	Identifiers	Link data on chemical identity	
Data Features	Identifiers	Link data using standard identifiers	
Data Features	Identifiers	Link to third party data through identifiers	
Data Features	Identifiers	Link together experiments and samples and data through Unique IDs	
Data Features	Identifiers	Researcher identification	
Data Features	Identifiers	Unique ID for experiments	
Data Features	Identifiers	Unique ID for samples	
Data Features	Identifiers	Link data and interpretation	
Data Features	Provenance	Display provenance of data	
Data Features	Provenance	Provenance of structures	
Data Features	Provenance	See algorithm/program used to produce data	
Data Features	Provenance	See how datasets are reused	
Data Features	Provenance	Tools to capture provenance	
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Automatic chemical recognition
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Global database of chemical values
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Handle reagents
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Import reaction
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Inbuilt understanding of molecules
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Include material information
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Standard list of instruments and reagents (remove instrument bits)
Domain Features	Based	Chemical/Molecules	Table of contents for specific reaction schemes

Domain Features	Based	Default Lists	Create default values
Domain Features	Based	Default Lists	Global database of chemical values
Domain Features	Based	Default Lists	List of data resources
Domain Features	Based	Default Lists	Standard list of instruments and reagents (remove instrument bits)
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Automatically capture data from instrument and upload to experiment
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Full availability of all sources, from firmware upwards for all devices and full open hardware
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Interface with equipment
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Link to instrument descriptions to view instructions
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Link to instruments
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Provide list of available equipment
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Remote control of instruments
Domain Features	Based	Equipment Interface	Standard list of instruments and reagents (remove reagents bit)
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Add dates to experiments
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Add titles to experiments
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Capture experiment conditions
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Copy and modify plan
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Create experiment plan
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Facilitate different experiments
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Keeping track of what environments and simulation parameters I've used for what results
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Mark experiments as completed
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Protocols

Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Provide full environment details for data generation
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Record experiment at each stage
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Record experiment conditions
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Record observations
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	ReCreate experimental conditions for verification
Domain Features	Based	Experiment Planning / Recording	Show experiment status
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Add safety information
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Automatically flag hazardous chemicals
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Automatically populate experiment record with risk assessment info
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Create risk phrase vocabulary
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Flag dangerous chemicals
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Index of COSHH materials
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Link to safety information
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Review safety information
Domain Features	Based	Health & Safety	Risk assessment inclusion
Domain Features	Based	LIMS/ELN	Link to Chemical Inventory Website
Domain Features	Based	LIMS/ELN	Link to ELN
Domain Features	Based	LIMS/ELN	Link to LIMS
Domain Features	Based	LIMS/ELN	Link to materials inventory system
Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based databases	Link to domain databases
Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based databases	Automatically link to external chemistry resources
Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based software	Link to domain software

Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based software	Interface between notebook and domain software
Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based software	Interface with chemspider
Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based software	Link to ChemDraw
Domain Features	Based	Link to domain-based software	Link to SciFinder
Generic Features		API Access	API / CMD access
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Update links
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Automate deletion of files of data that should not be published because of errors (e.g. in input).
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Automatic data cleaning/detecting faulty data
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Automatic processing and formatting
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Automatic updates of DRN
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Automation of routine tasks.
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Capture exploratory analysis Automatically
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Dropbox-esque features (automatic data update)
Generic Features		Automation Capabilities	Extract metadata associated with research data
Generic Features		General	Access planning, notes, data and analysis in one place
Generic Features		General	Easy to use systems that play well with one another
Generic Features		General	Interoperable services
Generic Features		General	Scalable
Generic Features		General	Simple to install
Generic Features		General	Simple to use
Generic Features		General	Simplified login (without multiple passwords)
Generic Features		General	Straightforward and transparent processes
Generic Features		General	User centric design
Generic Features		GUI	GUI access
Generic Features		Localisation	Language support
Generic Features		Localisation	See dates in appropriate timezones
Generic Features		Remote Access	Access from all locations
Generic Features		Remote Access	Access on low bandwidth systems
Generic Features		Remote Access	Remote desktop access to systems
Generic Features		Remote Access	synchronise across multiple devices
Generic Features		Remote Access	Use DRN offline
Generic Features		Synchronisation	Open several things simultaneously
Generic Features		Synchronisation	Upload large numbers of files simultaneously
Generic Features		Synchronisation	View multiple data/notes from different experiments

Metadata, Semantics & AI	AI Tools Integration /	Analyse Data
Metadata, Semantics & AI	AI Tools Integration /	Input search data into AI/ML workflows
Metadata, Semantics & AI	AI Tools Integration /	Provide large datasets for ML use
Metadata, Semantics & AI	AI Tools Integration /	Redirect AI from producing better models to do some of the heavy lifting in data wrangling
Metadata, Semantics & AI	AI Tools Integration /	Smoother integration of ml packages with existing data.
Metadata, Semantics & AI	AI Tools Integration /	Store ML training data
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Automated metadata creation & extraction (e.g. instrument settings, Code parameters, timestamps)
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Domain and general metadata
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Experiment metadata
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Extract metadata associated with research data
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Hierarchical metadata
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Metadata collection at source
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Metadata for samples
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Metadata in structured form
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Metadata knowledge graph
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Prepopulate metadata with specific vocabulary or predefined metadata schema
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Standard metadata and headers to data
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Store metadata
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Structure as required metadata (where appropriate)
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	Support variety of metadata formats
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Metadata	View others metadata in tag cloud
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Advanced Semantic Search (Filtered Search)
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Automatically link together related experiments
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Coherent standardisation of semantisation of materials data and processes to reach interoperability especially across data from electronic atomistic and mesoscopic scales experiments and simulations.

Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Inferences for similar projects
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Inferences for the same molecules of reactions
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Link everything together for me
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Link files / images / data
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Link raw, intermediate and analysed data
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Link related notebooks
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Link to measurement vocabularies
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Link to ontologies
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	More semantics. An easily searchable keywords lookup tool, that records the semantic meaning of the selected keywords. This would enable joined up research, without requiring researchers to understand ontologies. This should be used when publishing papers in addition to data, so it is easier to identify appropriate papers and data.
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Ontology driven workflows
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Prepopulate DRN with vocabulary or link to information system so links are Created
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Semantic annotations
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Tag / classify experiments
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Semantics	Tag / classify notes
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Templates	Create and use templates (public and private)
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Templates	Create flows from a list of standard components
Metadata, Semantics & AI	Templates	Use and Reuse stored models
Notebooking Features	Content support	Annotations and highlights
Notebooking Features	Content support	Audio files
Notebooking Features	Content support	Automatic handwriting recognition
Notebooking Features	Content support	Bar Codes/QR Codes for sample / experiment
Notebooking Features	Content support	Calculations / Formulas / Equations
Notebooking Features	Content support	Checklist with links
Notebooking Features	Content support	Copy sketches into notebook
Notebooking Features	Content support	Data/resources open in correct software
Notebooking Features	Content support	Facilitate sketches and drawing
Notebooking Features	Content support	Facilitate tables
Notebooking Features	Content support	Free text entry

Notebooking Features	Content support	Graph display of data
Notebooking Features	Content support	Handwritten notes
Notebooking Features	Content support	Import literature source
Notebooking Features	Content support	Include reaction scheme
Notebooking Features	Content support	Include structural representations (2D and 3D)
Notebooking Features	Content support	Integrate / store: Excel, Word, PDFs, Pictures,
Notebooking Features	Content support	Numerical entry
Notebooking Features	Content support	Photos / images
Notebooking Features	Content support	Postit notes
Notebooking Features	Content support	Record timings
Notebooking Features	Content support	Support complex images (giga-pixel, z-stacked, hyperspectral imaging)
Notebooking Features	Content support	Support obsolete file formats (future/past proofing)
Notebooking Features	Content support	Text recognition
Notebooking Features	Content support	Thumbnails of documents, graphs etc.
Notebooking Features	Content support	Timelines
Notebooking Features	Content support	TODO Lists
Notebooking Features	Content support	Videos
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	As easy to write in as a paper notebook
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Both human and machine access
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Digital pen integration
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Hands free/voice control
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Tablet/Smartphone compliant
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Usable in the lab like a paper notebook
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Voice Capture
Notebooking Features	Interaction / Access	Web based/Platform Independent
Notebooking Features	Link to other files	Link to Code
Notebooking Features	Link to other files	Link to data from other sources
Notebooking Features	Link to other files	Link to external dataset
Notebooking Features	Link to other files	Link to other experiments
Notebooking Features	Organisation / Reconfiguration	Contents Table / Overview Screen
Notebooking Features	Organisation / Reconfiguration	Group together team members and notebooks by topic
Notebooking Features	Organisation / Reconfiguration	Re-orderable list of work
Notebooking Features	Organisation / Reconfiguration	Timeline of experiments / studies by team/project/researcher/topic
Notebooking Features	Organisation / Reconfiguration	View experiments in last edited order

Notebooking Features	Paper Integration	Digitise paper based legacy data
Notebooking Features	Paper Integration	Handwritten notes
Notebooking Features	Paper Integration	Link with paper notebooks
Notebooking Features	Paper Integration	Scan in documents
Notebooking Features	Paper Integration	Transform/migrate digital legacy data
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Access to reference quality data
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Add Code citations
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Add data citations
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Easy access to published work
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Export literature references from notebooks for use in formal report
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Extract data Automatically from legacy literature
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Import literature source
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Journal article links
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Link to reference managers
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Link to reference managers
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Share literature resource
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Store and view literature sources
Notebooking Features	Referencing & Literature	Suggested citations
Notebooking Features	Word Processing	Cut and paste between windows
Notebooking Features	Word Processing	Smart cut and paste (e.g. matching field names)
Notebooking Features	Word Processing	Spell Checker
Notebooking Features	Word Processing	Word processing
Notebooking Features	Word Processing	WYSIWIG Editor for notes
Publishing & Sharing Features	Documentation & Instructions	Create instructions
Publishing & Sharing Features	Documentation & Instructions	Documentation for techniques
Publishing & Sharing Features	Documentation & Instructions	Share instructions
Publishing & Sharing Features	Documentation & Instructions	User documentation
Publishing & Sharing Features	DOIs	DOI generation / permanent links for data

Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Common data standards for import/export
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Downloads/Printing
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export all components of work (e.g. data, Code, graphics)
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export data to chemspider
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export full notebook
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export in multiple formats
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export literature references from notebooks for use in formal report
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export structures in compatible file formats
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Migration tools
Publishing & Sharing Features	Export	Export thesis
Publishing & Sharing Features	Licensing	Create Code licenses
Publishing & Sharing Features	Licensing	Create data licenses
Publishing & Sharing Features	Open Access	Default model for making data open once published
Publishing & Sharing Features	Open Access	Free scientific articles
Publishing & Sharing Features	Open Access	Use open source software (where possible)
Publishing & Sharing Features	Open Access	Lower Costs
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	Create package of notes/data/Code
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	Generate report button
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	Methods for publishing data
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	Produce paper publication
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	Thesis generation button
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	View reports
Publishing & Sharing Features	Publishing	Write report
Publishing & Sharing Features	Repositories	Download data from repository
Publishing & Sharing Features	Repositories	Find add and run Code from online repository

Publishing & Sharing Features	Repositories	Upload Code to repository
Publishing & Sharing Features	Repositories	Upload data to repository
Publishing & Sharing Features	Repositories	Upload notebooks to repository
Publishing & Sharing Features	Researcher Attribution	Attribution for combined datasets
Publishing & Sharing Features	Researcher Attribution	Recognition of researcher contribution to data
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Established data sharing expectations / policies
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Share data for reuse
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Share draft data with collaborators
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Share plan
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Share with other institutions
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Share work with collaborators
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Shareable files
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Shared electronic notebooks
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Shared files / notebooks
Publishing & Sharing Features	Sharing	Sharing and accessing large data
Publishing & Sharing Features	Social Media	Integrate with Social Media
Searching	Characteristics Search	Find datasets with specific characteristics
Searching	Domain Search	Making it easier to locate the necessary information and source on studied materials.
Searching	Domain Search	Search by structure
Searching	Domain Search	Search experiment protocols
Searching	Domain Search	Searches include reaction schemes
Searching	Indexing	Indexable
Searching	Indexing	Make things easier to find.
Searching	Indexing	Uniformity of interfaces to data bases and easily accessible search engines for extracting data.
Searching	Keyword/Concept Search via Content Types	Describe datasets to enable searching
Searching	Keyword/Concept Search via Content Types	Find context for the work

Searching	Keyword/Concept Search via Content Types	Keyword Search
Searching	Literature Search	Literature search
Searching	Notebook Search	Search notebook discussion forum
Searching	Notebook Search	Search through previous documents of a project
Searching	Notebook Search	Searchable data across all notebooks
Searching	Similarity Search	Search for similar data
Searching	Similarity Search	See related content upon click
Searching	Visual Search	Search by image
Searching	Visual Search	Search graphs (visual)
Training & User Support	Training	Training
Training & User Support	User Documentation	User Documentation

F. GraphQL

One technology that could be implemented to facilitate the interaction with services is GraphQL which could act as an intermediary between the notebook and the services. GraphQL specifies how information is exchanged between client and server and can be implemented in any programming language.

At the most basic level a GraphQL application sends a query to a service asking for specific fields for an object. A schema is passed to the GraphQL server and the server returns the same schema populated with the results. What makes GraphQL different from REST API calls is that rather than multiple end-points with fixed data structures, a GraphQL server exposes a single end-point with precisely the data that the client asked for. This means that a whole data request can be made in one go rather than having to send multiple separate requests to get all of the data required. It also means that superfluous data is not returned to client. It is possible to precisely define the data you want, and replacing multiple REST requests with a single call¹. This minimises the amount of data needing to be transmitted across the network and improving the efficiency of the applications, particularly for mobile usage. This also means that different clients can be developed to serve different needs that can request just the information that they want from the server, rather than needing a different server application for each different type of client application and also allows new functionality to be developed for the clients without needing to update the server application. GraphQL also has the concept of subscriptions where a client subscribes to an event and maintains a steady connection to the server so the client is informed when new objects are created matching the requested type.

GraphQL has its own type system that is used to define the schema of an API, the syntax for writing schemas is called Schema Definition Language (SDL). Defining schemas and even sophisticated queries are relatively simple. GraphQL types have unique IDs generated by the server when new objects are created. GraphQL can not only be used to fetch data, but it can also be used to add, modify, or delete data through mutations. The SDL Schema specifies the capabilities of the API and defines how clients can request the data. There are 3 primary architectures that include a GraphQL server: a GraphQL server with a connected database, a GraphQL server as a layer in front of a number of third-party systems enabling them to be integrated through a single GraphQL API, and a hybrid approach of the two where the GraphQL API integrates a connected database and third-party applications. GraphQL is database and transport-layer agnostic, so it does not matter what technology or format is used for the database or third-party data sources, and so enables the complexity of the existing systems can be hidden.

Figure F. 1: System outline for GraphQL and GraphQL with connected database

With GraphQL the client application does not need to know where the data from the request is coming from, and this takes away the requirement for the user to have to specify which services to use and therefore the client can be designed for the way that the user needs it to work, rather than fit around the design of the service provider's API. The client application is responsible for just describing the data requirements and displaying the data in the user interface. Resolver functions specify how the types and fields in the schema are connected to various backends and from where the data from the queries will be fetched. There is a resolver for each field in the schema and each resolver knows how to fetch the data for that field. The GraphQL server goes through three processes to respond to a query: Parse, validate and execute. The query takes the shape of a tree and waits for the results at the top level before moving onto the next step down in the tree, so that data can be fetched for each matching item at each level. At the end of the process the server collects all the information together in the schema structure to send to the client. Catalysis-Hub.org is an example of a chemistry-related project that makes use of GraphQL for sending and receiving queries to a web-based interface from a database of surface reactionsⁱⁱ.

Apollo is a GraphQL platform that would be useful to investigate, with a free version that would enable the building of applications and testingⁱⁱⁱ. Apollo has both a client and server application that works with popular frameworks for building user interfaces and for interacting with databases and other services.

The use of a tool such as GraphQL could have the potential to enable DRNs to be tailored through the development of 'class of service' specific plug-ins. The interface for the plug-in would be correlated to the GraphQL Query Schema that would be sent to the server. The server-side application could then contain the knowledge and logic to connect to the available service providers to retrieve the information, or execute the appropriate mutations where data is to be modified or added.

ⁱ Hartig, O.; Pérez, J. Semantics and Complexity of GraphQL. In *Proceedings of the 2018 World Wide Web Conference, WWW '18*; International World Wide Web Conferences Steering Committee: Republic and Canton of Geneva, CHE, 2018; pp 1155–1164. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3178876.3186014>.

ⁱⁱ Winther, K.T., Hoffmann, M.J., Boes, J.R. *et al.* Catalysis-Hub.org, an open electronic structure database for surface reactions. *Sci Data* **6**, 75 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0081-y>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.apollographql.com>